

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

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Summary and objective of the deliverable

With the increasing number of targeted therapies approved in the same indication in oncology and the increasing complexity of tumour profiles, molecular screening programs have been further implemented in clinical routine to facilitate access to matched therapies via the organisation of Molecular Tumour Boards (MTBs). MTBs have been implemented in several cancer centres worldwide and include different specialists (mainly medical oncologists, haematologists, pathologists, geneticists, medical biologists, computational biologists, pharmacists and radiologists) involved in tumour profiling, molecular alterations' interpretation and treatment decision. However, it can differ widely across MTBs, since no standard procedures, quality requirements or guidelines have been published to date. Standard guidelines and harmonization are still needed.

The Deliverable 8.1 aims to describe the different organizations of MTB across countries and institutions of the consortium. This description also includes the NGS panel types used and patient selection criteria for genomic screening per country.

The objective is to establish the structure and operation of MTBs across various European countries.

Work performed

In order to collect information regarding local MTBs across institutions and European countries, two actions have been carried out:

1. Partners from the consortium were asked to fill a template of 2 pages to collect MTBs organization across countries (Figure 1)
2. A survey was created together with WP9 (Treatment and follow-up) and WP10 (Oncology decision support tools) to collect qualitative & quantitative information (Figure 2). The analysis of the results of the survey will be the subject of an independent report and will help to complete deliverables D8.2 and D8.3

The survey was accessible online via the following link:

<https://forms.microsoft.com/e/WQjN5n2edD>

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MTB ORGANIZATION

Institution _____

Country _____

Participants to this form _____

Type of MTB _____

General description of MTB
Objectives: frequency, participants and multidisciplinary roles (medical, scientist, management and administrative if relevant), link to national initiatives, engagement strategy for patients ...

Objectives:

Participants & Responsibilities (including administrative & medical management profiles if relevant) :

Contact & links:

Frequency:

Engagement strategy for patients:

Samples and data flow
General workflows of both samples and data for the NGS analysis

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Reporting of alterations
Somatic and germline alterations reporting in MTB conclusions

MTB endpoints and follow-up

Synthetic description of the endpoints :

Endpoint categories (please check the following endpoints when relevant to your MTB):

Endpoint category	Endpoint subcategory	MTB endpoints (check when relevant)	Details
Patient/Healthcare professionals	Access to high throughput molecular screening		
	Outcome		
	Access to innovative drugs/trials		
	Patient-reported experience measures		
Healthcare providers and administrative	MTB activity		
	Process (workflows and communication)		
Economic impact	Medico-economic evaluation		

If applicable, which decision support tool (DST) does the MTB use?
(ex: Clonality, Navis, QCI, Integrit, Seacore, etc.)

Figure 1. Template sent to partners of the consortium for MTB organization description

Figure 2. Sections of the survey

Results

Templates completed were received from 12 institutions. More precisely this includes 14 different MTBs from 6 different countries, distributed as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Participants enrol in the 2-pages questionnaire

Results are reported below, for more details please refer to the Annexes.

I. MTBs objectives

The different participant reported the objectives of their respective MTBs which are reported in Table 1. Globally, the objective of the MTBs is to allow patients access to innovative trials and/or therapeutic option through molecular screening.

Institution, country	MTBs objectives
IRE, IT	To identify actionable alterations outside approved indications (mainly OncoKB levels 3A/B). Secondary aim: assignment of non-standard therapy and evaluation of clinical outcome.
Charité, DE	To find an interdisciplinary consensus on therapeutic starting points after receiving molecular pathological diagnostics
Curie local MTB, FR	To refer patients with metastatic cancer in recurrence or progression, or with a rare cancer, towards a clinical trial with innovative molecules, based on the tumor molecular characterisation.

Curie national MTB, FR	To organize the management of patients with metastatic cancer whose primary origin could not be determined on the histological markers independently of the stage of the disease and treatments received.
APHP solid tumours, FR	To organize the management of patients with a rare cancer and patients with a non hematological solid tumor in therapeutic failure (across APHP)
APHP acute leukemias, FR	To organize the management of patients with relapsed/refractory acute lymphoblastic and acute myeloid leukemia (at national level)
BSMO, BE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify patients with molecular alterations that can be targeted with standard of care or in genotype-driven clinical trials - Build and share knowledge - Facilitate patient referral between centres
Antoine Lacassagne, FR	To propose early phases of clinical trials and/or the prescription of new treatments, which are not routinely available, to patients who are in treatment failure
UCCSH, DE	To optimize the diagnosis and therapy of patients with rare or advanced cancers (solid and haematological), lacking guideline-based therapeutic options
ICO, ES	To refer patients with certain clinical contexts to molecular determination, allowing the selection of patients with molecular characteristics of interest to be orientated towards specific targeted treatments.
MUW, PL	To discuss patients who are treated in the Dept of Neurosurgery with gliomas and other tumors of the CNS (including metastatic cancer to the brain) towards an integrated pathological and molecular diagnosis and also to guide patient to clinical trials based on the tumor molecular characterisation.
MSCI, PL	To verify additional therapeutic options in rare cancer populations or in patients who failed to the standard of care.
CHU Lille, FR	To organize the management of patients with solid tumors requiring molecular diagnostics.
CHU Bordeaux, FR	To organize the management of large comprehensive molecular screening for patients to allow them access to innovative therapies available in clinical trials or compassionate access (ACC).

Table 1. MTBs objectives according to participants' answers

II. Frequency and main participants

Following the assessment of the 14 MTBs, the majority of the meetings are virtual as reported in Table 2. Their frequency is either bi-weekly or weekly with one MTB being twice a week, and one MTB set up “ad-hoc” upon request. These data suggests the need for these meetings across institutions and countries.

Institution	Frequency	Type
IRE, IT	bi-weekly	Virtual
Charité, DE	weekly	Both
Curie local MTB, FR	weekly	Virtual
Curie national MTB, FR	bi-weekly	Virtual
APHP solid tumours, FR	bi-weekly	Virtual
APHP acute leukemias, FR	bi-weekly	Virtual
BSMO, BE	weekly	Virtual
Antoine Lacassagne, FR	weekly	in-person
UCCSH, DE	bi-weekly	Both
ICO, ES	twice a week	in-person
MUW, PL	Ad-hoc	NA
MSCI, PL	weekly	NA

CHU Lille, FR	bi-weekly	Virtual
CHU Bordeaux, FR	bi-weekly	Virtual

Table 2. Frequencies and types of MTBs meetings

Different multi-disciplinary specialists are present during the MTBs to drive the discussions. A summary of the different experts is reported in Figure 4 and shows that oncologists and molecular biologists / biotechnologists are systematically present.

On the other hand, biostatisticians, bioinformaticians, clinical study coordinators and biobank representatives are only present in less than 15% of the MTBs which could be improved.

MTB coordinators or scientific secretaries are present in 64% of the MTBs included in the assessment showing the need to allocate dedicated personnel for the coordination of these multi-disciplinary meetings and subsequent workflows.

Figure 4. MTB Participants profiles

III. National initiatives linked to MTB

Some of the MTBs are linked to national initiatives detailed below In Table 3.

IRE, IT	Regional: Agreements with 7 cancer centres in the greater Rome area
Charité, DE	National: NCT MASTER Program (https://www.nct-heidelberg.de/forschung/molecular-stratification/master.html)
Curie (local and national), FR	National: Plan France Médecine Génomique (PFMG) 2025 (https://pfm2025.aviesan.fr/)
APHP solid tumours, FR	National: Plan France Médecine Génomique (PFMG) 2025 (https://pfm2025.aviesan.fr/)
APHP acute leukemias, FR	National: Plan France Médecine Génomique (PFMG) 2025 (https://pfm2025.aviesan.fr/)

BSMO, BE	PRECISION Belgium initiative (doi:10.1016/j.esmoop.2022.100524)
Centre Antoine Lacassagne, FR	National: Plan France Médecine Génomique (PFMG) 2025 (https://pfm2025.aviesan.fr/) Regional: Hospital platform for molecular genetics of cancers in the PACA-Est region, which includes various laboratories
UCCSH, DE	NA
ICO, ES	NA
MUW, PL	NA
MSCI, PL	NA
CHU Lille, FR	National: Plan France Médecine Génomique (PFMG) 2025 (https://pfm2025.aviesan.fr/)
CHU Bordeaux, FR	National: Plan France Médecine Génomique (PFMG) 2025 (https://pfm2025.aviesan.fr/) Regional: Rare tumors networks labeled byINCa , as for example CARADERM, GFELC, REFCOR, POLA, RENATEN...

Table 3. National initiatives linked to MTBs assessed

IV. Patients selection and engagement strategy

The patients' criteria that are suitable for MTB discussion in each participating centres are reported in Table 4. Generally, patients with advanced and/or metastatic or cancers are discussed in MTB.

IRE, IT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient referred by an oncologist or medical doctor with any neoplastic condition • >18 yr • no standard treatment options • available tumour tissue and/or circulating tumour DNA • Performance Status (PS) ≤ 2 • Informed consent signed
Charité, DE	Missing info
Curie local MTB, FR	Patient registered by a physician and at least one of the three conditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The patient had a consultation with one of the clinicians of Institut Curie, and a pathology report is available in the medical record. - The patient's case was previously discussed in a regional MTB for which Institut Curie is the reference centre and a PFMG 2025 (SeqOIA) prescription has been validated. - The patient referred to Institut Curie for a PFMG 2025 analysis under the pre-indications of "Rare Cancers" or "Metastatic adult solid tumour" (https://pfm2025.aviesan.fr/professionnels/pre-indications-et-mise-en-place/), and frozen tumour material is available.
Curie national MTB, FR	Any patient with metastatic cancer, for which the primary origin could not be determined.
APHP solid tumours, FR	Any cancer patient with therapeutic failure or any patient with a rare cancer at any time of the disease
APHP acute leukemias, FR	Any patient with relapsed or refractory AML or ALL eligible for active therapies, including after allogeneic hematopoietic cell transplantation, can be registered.
BSMO, BE	All solid tumour cases with comprehensive genomic profiling are eligible to be discussed.
Antoine Lacassagne, FR	Any adult patient with advanced cancer or for which there is no therapeutic standard (rare cancers), a performance status (PS) equal to or less than 1, and who has not had multiple cancers simultaneously.
UCCSH, DE	Patients with advanced cancer, progress after standard therapy. Patients without a promising treatment option. Patients with a rare entity/molecular pathological profile. Patients with unusual clinical courses. Patients are suitable for experimental therapy.

ICO, ES	Patients are selected based on level one genes and tumour types as described for the Catalan Health and subjected to reimbursement or with potential inclusion in active clinical trials.
MUW, PL	Any patient with a brain tumor (either CNS origin or metastatic) who needs to be discussed either before neurosurgery (to discuss treatment and diagnostic options), or after neurosurgery (when the pathology report and/or genetical report is available).
MSCI, PL	Rare cancer populations or in patients who failed to the standard of care
CHU Lille, FR	Patients with solid tumors requiring molecular diagnostics
CHU Bordeaux, FR	Solid tumours and lymphomas in adults

Table 4. Patients' selection criteria for MTB discussion

Regarding patient engagement strategy, only Charité is working on this aspect. At Charité, patient advocacy groups are involved within a patient advisory board.

This aspect should be developed in the future but communications regarding molecular testing, MTBs and possible orientation to clinical trials towards oncologists and patients were set in the different countries.

V. NGS tests performed

The types of NGS analysis that are performed *via* the different MTBs are described in Figure 5.

IRE, IT	NGS on tDNA and ctDNA: ThermoFischer panels, Illumina, FoundationOne or WGS+WES+RNAseq
Charité, DE	Panels and WGS+RNA-seq
Curie local, FR	DNA NGS panel in-house (571 genes) + targeted RNAseq panel for fusion detection; or WGS+WES+RNAseq
Curie national, FR	WGS+WES+RNAseq
APHP solid tumours, FR	WGS+WES+RNAseq
APHP acute leukemias, FR	WGS+WES+RNAseq
BSMO, BE	FoundationOne CDx, FoundationOne Liquid CDx, FoundationOne Heme (rare tumours), Illumina TruSight Oncology 500
Antoine Lacassagne, FR	WGS+WES+RNAseq or NGS panel, MSI, RNAseq, SNParray, GREAT/HRR, etc.
USCCH, DE	IHC, FISH, WES/RNAseq
ICO, ES	TruSight Oncology 500 (Illumina) and Oncomine Precision Assay (ThermoFisher).
MUW, PL	DNA NGS panel custom (>300 genes) + qPCR for MGMT promotor methylation
MSCI, PL	FoundationOne medicine panel
CHU Lille, FR	WGS+WES+RNAseq NGS targeted DNA and RNA panels MSI analysis methylation analysis (MGMT, MLH1, methylome, CGH-array)
CHU Bordeaux, FR	Comprehensive panel/FMI/WES/WGS & RNAseq

Figure 5. NGS analyses were performed in the different MTBs. (Genome-wide approaches = WES, WGS, total RNAseq).

Genome wide-approaches are mainly used (71%) of the MTBs assessed in the questionnaire and are mainly related to national initiatives for genomics. Commercial panels for DNA or RNA testing are still used in 64% of the MTBs, while in-house panels are used in only 3/14 MTB (21%).

VI. Samples and data flow description

Samples and data flows depend on each Institution. A summary of the steps is detailed below.

IRE, IT	<p>Step 1: informed consent.</p> <p>Step 2: case presentation during the first round of collegial discussion.</p> <p>Step 3: genomic profiling, mostly involving NGS on tDNA and ctDNA.</p> <p>Step 4: joint appointment of two case discussants, providing distinct pieces of expertise, clinical and molecular.</p> <p>Step 5: case review in a second discussion round (typically 15 days later) and MTB recommendations.</p>
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	Step 6: treatment recommendation.
Charité, DE	<p>Sequencing for panels is done on routine platforms, and genome-wide analyses (WGS, RNA-seq) are done via our central sequencing core.</p> <p>Raw data analysis will be performed within the pathology / Labor Berlin bioinformatics teams.</p> <p>Within the NCT MASTER program, there are also joint weekly discussions of patients entered into the program</p> <p>Patients can be enrolled in the national program initiative.</p> <p>Standard pipelines are used for data analysis.</p>
Curie (local and national), FR	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) the referring physician registers the patient for local MTB 2) MTB 1: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation of the indication • Choice of samples/tools for the analyses: 2 possible workflows for molecular analyses via Institut Curie local MTB: Internal prescription or PFMG 2025 (SeqOIA) prescription. For National MTB, PFMG 2025 (SeqOIA or AURAGEN) prescription is done. 3) For PFMG analysis: Medical consultation, a signature of consent and samples shipment (tumour and blood) to corresponding sites for extraction and sequencing platform for sequencing 4) Pathological qualification of the sample + nucleic acids extraction 5) Clinical and biological data integration + molecular analyses 6) MTB 2: Review of the alterations validated by medical biologists and treatment proposition. For the national MTB, a diagnosis can be proposed (carcinoma of unknown primary)
APHP solid tumours, FR	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The referring physician registers the patient for MTB rare cancer or therapeutic failure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upstream MTB: Validation of the indication and PFMG 2025 (SeqOIA) prescription 2) Medical consultation, signature of consent and sample shipment (tumor and blood) to corresponding platforms for nucleic acid extraction 3) WES/WGS & RNAseq by the SeqOIA platform 4) Validation of results and molecular reports by molecular biologists 5) Downstream MTB: Review of the genetic alterations reported by the molecular biologists and proposition of a diagnosis and/or therapeutic option
APHP acute leukemias, FR	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) the referring physician registers the patient for the national MTB 2) Upstream MTB: Validation of the indication and PFMG 2025 (SeqOIA or AURAGEN) prescription 3) Medical consultation, a signature of consent and samples shipment (tumour and blood) to corresponding sites for extraction and sequencing platform for sequencing 4) WES/WGS & RNAseq 5) Validation of results and molecular reports 6) Optionally, ex vivo drug testing on the NEXT-AML (AML) or ALL-TARGET (T-ALL) platforms. 7) MTB 2 (“downstream”): <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Review of the alterations reported by the molecular biologists b. Refinement of the prognostic assessment, potential diagnostic reassessment, and suggestion of one or several therapeutic options (either based on the newly proposed diagnosis, or prognosis or based on a druggable molecular alteration or functional dependence).
BSMO, BE	<p>Step 1: 2 sources of cases are discussed in the national MTB:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GeNeo (NCT04641676): central testing at Foundation Medicine - BALLETT (NCT05058937): local testing with the Trusight Oncology 500 (Illumina) by a consortium of 9 NGS laboratories, according to a predefined run-schedule (weekly alternating between participating laboratories) <p>Step 2: discussion of molecular results of panels NGS in the national MTB and recommendations into 5 categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standard of care local or commercial NGS - Genotype-driven clinical trial - PRECISION 2 Program of basket trials - Genotype-driven standard of care - Pharma access program <p>Step 3: all MTBs related data are registered into the PRECISION 1 database</p>
Antoine	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The CRA registers the patient for PACA EST MTB.

Lacassagne, FR	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2) MTB 1: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verification of eligibility criteria • Proposal of molecular analyses • PFMG 2025 (AURAGEN [https://www.auragen.fr/] platform) prescription: WGS, WES and RNAseq 3) Medical consultation, a signature of consent and samples shipment (tumour and blood) to corresponding sites for extraction and sequencing platform for sequencing 4) WES/WGS & RNAseq OR NGS panel, MSI, RNAseq, SNParray, GREAT/HRR, etc. 5) Validation of results and molecular reports 6) MTB 2: Review of the alterations reported by the molecular biologists and proposition of early phases clinical trials and/or prescription of new treatments which are not routinely available.
USCCH, DE	<p>Step 1: The patient registered by a physician</p> <p>Step 2: The pathology department checks for suitable patient material availability (most recent preferred). The MTB coordination checks for the existence of germline controls and consent declarations. If necessary, a request for the transmission of externally available material is initiated. Detailed documentation of the patient history, lines of treatment, response to treatments, available material and diagnostic tests already performed are documented in the hospital information system ORBIS.</p> <p>Step 3: A diagnostic recommendation is discussed by an interdisciplinary expert group on a case-by-case basis. The MTB coordination will order the respective molecular diagnostics at the department of pathology, initiating the implementation and reporting of molecular diagnostics.</p> <p>Step 4: molecular tests (IHC, FISH, WES/RNAseq)</p> <p>Step 5: diagnostic report created.</p> <p>Step 6: results are discussed in a second MTB and recommendations are made.</p>
ICO, ES	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The referring physician registers the sample in the SAP application 2) The process to the anatomical pathology department 3) Archival samples are identified and processed 4) DNA/RNA extraction, library preparation and sequencing 5) Data analysis, curation of variants (manual) 6) Discussion of the results to identify potential treatments and clinical trials
MUW, PL	NA
MSCI, PL	Foundation One reports or similar which are available only as a part of clinical trials
CHU Lille, FR	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) the referring physician registers the patient for local MTB 2) MTB 1: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation of the indication • Check of tissue availability and quality for the analyses and prescription is done. 3) For PFMG analysis: Medical consultation, a signature of consent and samples shipment (tumour and blood) to corresponding sites for extraction and sequencing platform for sequencing 4) Pathological qualification of the sample + nucleic acids extraction 5) Clinical and biological data integration + molecular analyses <p>MTB 2 for PFMG analyses is common with Institut Curie local MTB: Review of the alterations validated by medical biologists and treatment proposition. For the national MTB, a diagnosis can be proposed (carcinoma of unknown primary).</p> <p>For other analyses, MTB2 is not systematic for all cases, only upon request.</p>
CHU Bordeaux, FR	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) the referring physician registers the patient for regional MTB 2) MTB 1: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation of the indication • Decision of local testing by comprehensive panel TSO 500 Illumina • Decision of further sampling or to perform liquid biopsy analysis through Foundation One • PFMG 2025 (AURAGEN [https://www.auragen.fr/] platform) prescription: WGS, WES and RNAseq 3) Medical consultation, signature of consent and samples shipment (tumour and blood) to corresponding sites for extraction and sequencing platform for sequencing 4) Comprehensive panel/FMI/WES/WGS & RNAseq 5) Data integration

	<p>6) Validation of results and molecular reports</p> <p>7) MTB 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of the alterations reported by the molecular biologists • Proposition of a diagnosis and/or therapeutic solution (either based on the newly proposed diagnostic or based on a druggable molecular alteration) <p>Referring physicians are notified and invited to participate on both MTB 1 and MTB 2.</p> <p>The MTB 2 conclusions and the molecular results are send by secure email to the corresponding external referring physician. For CHU de Bordeaux patients, both results and conclusions are also integrated directly into the biopathology and medical records.</p>
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Table 5. Sample and data flow steps

VII. Reporting of alterations in MTB conclusions

Alterations reported in each MTB conclusion are summarized in Table 6. This concerns both somatic alterations (gene types, variants, treatment recommendation) and germline alterations.

IRE, IT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Somatic: MTB recommendations as per international databases, such as ESCAT and OncoKB, and the literature. And after careful evaluation of costs/benefits - Germline: handled as an incidental finding and referred to our heredofamilial cancer unit
Charité, DE	<p>Somatic alterations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data interpretation is done using both: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o commercial products such as MH Guide supporting clinical decision-making o in-house tools and expert team evaluations <p>Treatment recommendations: a clinical trial match team looks for available treatment options for the patients both locally, within the extended NCT network and Germany-wide.</p> <p>Germline: NA</p>
Curie local and national, FR	<p>Somatic alterations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gene classifications: oncoKB, COSMIC databases, literature - Variants classification: in-house referential, ACMG international classification (ESP6500 & gnomAD, COSMIC, oncoKB & ClinVar, IARC TP53 & BRCAshare) - Treatment recommendation: clinical trial national database or according to available targeted drugs, and based on patient medical history <p>CNV, MSI status, HRD, TMB and the description of the mutational signature are also reported.</p> <p>For national CUP MTB, a classifier tool based on the training of a variational autoencoder to predict tissue of origin based on the RNA-sequencing data has been integrated into the analysis pipeline. The result of the classifier is reported in MTB conclusions</p> <p>Germline: MTB only reports suspicion of germline alteration based on the results of the somatic analysis, and recommends a genetic consultation for the patient, outside of the MTB.</p>
APHP solid tumours, FR	<p>Somatic alterations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gene classifications: oncoKB, COSMIC databases, literature - Variants classification: in-house referential, ACMG international classification (ESP6500 & gnomAD, COSMIC, oncoKB & ClinVar, IARC TP53 & BRCAshare) - Treatment recommendation: NA <p>CNV, MSI status, a score HRD, and the description of the mutational signature are also reported. Several signatures based on WTS are also reported to better classify the tumour or to orientate the treatment.</p> <p>Germline: MTB only reports suspicion of germline alteration based on the results of the somatic</p>

	analysis, and recommends a genetic consultation for the patient, outside of the MTB.
APHP acute leukemias, FR	NA
BSMO, BE	<p>Somatic alterations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GeNeo: standard FMI reporting (PDF), including the treatment recommendations - BALLET: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o SNVs and small indels are biologically classified according to the Belgian ComPerMed guidelines. Amplifications and fusions, TMB values, MSI and HRD results are also retrieved from the TSO500 data analysis pipeline. o All alterations are clinically classified according to Li et al (ASCO/CAP/AMP; TierIA, B; Tier IIC, D). o Proposals for treatment recommendations are registered by local sites in an eCRF and discussed during the pre-MTB NGS lab meeting where mainly the classification of variants is discussed and agreed upon. o During the MTB, a custom-designed app is used for i) Visualization and presentation of the clinical and molecular data to the MTB members (in MS Teams), ii) Linking to gene-drug match database, iii) Discussing the proposed treatment recommendations by linking to relevant websites (eg. ClinicalTrials.gov) and iv) Discussing, finalizing and prioritizing treatment recommendations (eg. Approved treatments, clinical trials, medical need programs, off-label drug use) <p>Germline: MTB only reports suspicion of germline alteration based on the results of the somatic analysis, and recommends a genetic consultation for the patient, outside of the MTB.</p>
Antoine Lacassagne, FR	<p>Somatic alterations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gene classification: NA - Variants classification: according to 5 different classes according to UNCseq (Hayes and Kim, J Clin Invest, 2015, PMID:25642706). - The SNP array carried out in the LGTS allows to generate a summary table of the quantitative genomic anomalies of interest in the context of PACA EST MTB. - Treatment recommendation: no classification used, only based on clinical trials and treatment availability <p>Germline: NA</p>
USCCH, DE	<p>Somatic alterations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gene classification: the selection of the genes examined is based on the current list of the American College of Medical Genomics (PMID: 34012068) and the list of actionable genes from OncoKB - Variants classification: according to 5 different classes according to UNCseq (Hayes and Kim, J Clin Invest, 2015, PMID:25642706). - CNV, MSI status, a score HRD, and a BRCAness score are also reported - Treatment recommendations: based on extensive research in available databases and literature. An evidence level according to the National Centre for Tumour Diseases (NCT)/ German Consortium for Translational Cancer Research (DKTK) classification is reported and prioritized when possible. <p>Germline: The patient gives consent to evaluate genetic alterations in a defined set of oncogenes and other disease-related genes at the germline level. Beyond the genes selected for somatic analysis, no further evaluation of the germline data takes place. If a relevant alteration in the germline is identified, genetic counselling is offered.</p>
ICO, ES	<p>Somatic alterations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Classification based on CatSalut's guidelines, in ESCAT Tiers and OncoKB levels classifications. The interpretation of the molecular results is reported in the NSG report done by biologists and discussed in MTB. - Treatment recommendations: In case no targeted therapy is available for reimbursement in the healthcare system (Sistema Català de Salut, CatSalut), clinicians from the Phase I clinical trials unit assess if there are open clinical trials for those patients that may not have other available treatment options.

	<p>Germline: If a pathogenic variant is suspected to be germline (following ESMO guidelines), the patient will be referred to the genetic counselling unit.</p>
MUW, PL	<p>Somatic and germline alterations are listed in a NGS report which is done by the molecular biologists and discussed in MTB.</p> <p>Somatic alterations :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variants classification: in-house referential, AMP/ACMG international classification (ESP6500 & gnomAD, COSMIC, oncoKB & ClinVar) - The classification allows to classify variants according to 4 different classes as recommended for somatic variants: pathogenic; likely pathogenic; variant of uncertain significance; benign. The result is then adapted to somatic alterations taking into account the tumoral context (e.g. tumor cellularity, VAF, CNV, LOH, etc.) <p>Germline alterations :</p> <p>If the germline variant is suspected, additional consulting and verification is scheduled</p>
MSCI, PL	NA
CHU Lille, FR	Report only somatic alterations. The molecular report also mentions the type of tests that has been used, the genes that have been tested, and whether there are known to be associated with sensitivity or resistance to therapies.
CHU Bordeaux, FR	<p>Somatic alterations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gene classifications: oncoKB, COSMIC databases, literature - Variants classification: in-house referential, ACMG international classification (ESP6500 & gnomAD, COSMIC, InterVar, ClinVar, SIFT, Polyphen2 & PROVEAN), ESCO and GFCO. - Treatment recommendation: NA <p>CNV, MSI status, HRD, TMB and the description of the mutational signature are also reported.</p> <p>Germline: MTB only reports suspicion of germline alteration based on the results of the somatic analysis, and recommends a genetic consultation for the patient, outside of the MTB.</p>

Table 6. Alterations reported in MTBs

Regarding the germline alteration report in MTB conclusions, if a relevant alteration in the germline is identified, genetic counselling is suggested during MTB to give the results to the patient and potentially run additional tests separately from the MTB.

VIII. Endpoints evaluated

The categories of endpoints that are assessed in the different MTBs are reported in Figure 6 (except for MUW and MSCI MTBs which were recently created and do not have sufficient perspective yet). The majority of MTBs included the same categories of endpoints. The most frequent ones regard access to innovative drugs/trials, access to high throughput sequencing, processes of workflows and communication and patients' outcomes.

Medico-economic endpoints are monitored in only 33% which could be increased, as well as patient-reported experience measures that are only done in 17% of the MTBs.

Figure 6. Categories of endpoints assessed in the different MTBs

IX. Decision support tools (DSTs)

There is currently no consensus on the definition of a DST, making participants' responses heterogeneous. Here is the definition on which we based ourselves with WP10:

“Decision Support Tools (DST) are “computer systems designed to support healthcare providers facing a complex decision about individual patients at the point in time that these decisions are made.” For this survey, we focus on tools that translate NGS and relevant clinical data from individual patients to support the MTB in making decisions for the management and treatment of the individual patients.”

We can observe, in the responses from participants, a mix of both databases and DSTs. In total, 5/14 (36%) of the MTBs used at least one of these tools. The tools used were diverse, with only 2 tools/database used in several institutions (OncoKB and NAVIFY).

Institution	DST used
IRE, IT	OncoKB and Oncofuse Knowledgebase Reporter from ThermoFisher/Life Technologies
Charité, DE	MH Guide (https://www.molecularhealth.com/solutions/mh-guide/)
Curie local MTB, FR	None
Curie national MTB, FR	None
APHP solid tumours, FR	None
APHP acute leukemias, FR	OncoKB
BSMO, BE	FMI, NAVIFY, custom-designed trial-specific app, OncoKDM and CGW
Antoine Lacassagne, FR	NA
UCCSH, DE	None <i>cbiportal used to integrate sequencing data and clinical info. Prioritized recommendations discussed during MTB are manually integrated into cbiportal for a transfer back to the clinical</i>

	<i>information System</i>
ICO , ES	NAVIFY and genome databases (Alamut, Franklin)
MUW, PL	None yet
MSCI, PL	None yet
CHU Lille, FR	None
CHU Bordeaux, FR	None

Conclusion and impact

Globally, the aim of the MTBs is to discuss case-by-case patients and propose a potential therapeutic strategy, through access to innovative trials, based on molecular analyses and multidisciplinary discussion. Outcomes are also monitored in order to evaluate the impact of MTBs and molecular screening on patients' clinical care.

Eight out of fourteen MTBs are organized only virtually, which can contribute to save time and allows extra-institutional experts consultations. Their frequency is mainly bi-weekly or weekly, suggesting a strong demand for MTBs.

The types of experts mainly involved in the different MTBs are oncologists, molecular biologists and pathologists. Interestingly 64% of MTBs also include project managers and MTB coordination teams in the meetings to allow smoother workflows and follow-up of the different cases discussed.

The type of patients that are reviewed during MTB are mainly patients in therapeutic failure, refractory and/or metastatic, or patients with rare cancers.

The NGS test used for tumor characterization are genome-wide approaches, which can probably be explained by the diminution of NGS costs and the implementation of national initiative programs. When looking at the different participants to this questionnaire, it also appears that the countries that have participated may have the resources to implement a reimbursement and by extension support the development of molecular analyses techniques and MTBs. This also highlights that the reimbursement of the NGS costs should align with the development of MTB to reduce the gaps with other countries.

Regarding DSTs, only 36% of the MTBs surveyed used at least one tool. This point should be developed in order to better address patients towards appropriate trials and targeted therapies. Also, what is considered as a DST should be better defined.

MTB organization can vary but objectives and endpoints are similar. There is a need to harmonize the workflows and produce guidelines for data interpretation and ranking of alterations for treatment decision. Efforts still need to be made for molecular data use for diagnosis.

The data accumulated within the consortium will be key for future clinical trials and research exploitation. The integration of clinical and molecular data through common work with WP9, WP10 & WP11 will be useful to provide standardized guidelines for molecular interpretation that utilize reproducible bioinformatics pipelines (including machine learning approaches) to support treatment decision (WP9, WP10 & WP11).

The survey will provide more accurate data that will be used for the guidelines in D8.3.

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Annex I MTB organization Charité

Annex II MTB organization UCCSH

Annex III MTB organization IRE

Annex IV MTB organization APHP hematology

Annex V MTB organization Precision Belgium

Annex VI MTB organization Antoine Lacassagne

Annex VII MTB organization APHP solid tumors

Annex VIII MTB organization Institut Curie local MTB

Annex IX MTB organization Institut Curie national MTB

Annex X MTB organization ICO

Annex XI MTB organization MUW

Annex XII MTB organization MSCI

Annex XIII MTB organization CHU Lille

MTB ORGANIZATION

Institution	Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin
Country	Germany
Participants to this form	Lars Bullinger, Olga Blau
Type of MTB	Molecular Tumor Board – Center for Personalized Medicine

General description of MTB

Objectives, frequency, participants and multidisciplinary roles (medical, scientist, management and administrative if relevant), link to national initiatives, engagement strategy for patients ...

Objectives:

The molecular tumor conference serves to find an interdisciplinary consensus after receiving molecular pathological diagnostics. Based on the detected changes in the tumor profile, the development of an individual therapy concept is pursued. For this purpose, a detailed analysis of all changes found during sequencing is carried out, if necessary extended by immunohistological analysis, in order to understand the relevant drivers of tumor progression and to define therapeutic starting points.

Participants & Responsibilities (including administrative & medical management profiles if relevant) :

Team - Clinical and translational precision oncology consisting of experienced hemato-oncologists, pathologists, biologists, additional clinical experts if needed (radiologists, organ-specific oncologists, etc.)

Contact & links:

https://ccc.charite.de/leistungen/plattform_fuer_personalisierte_krebsmedizin_der_charite_ppk_c/molekulare_tumorkonferenz/

Frequency:

Weekly Charité MTB, and weekly joint NCT MASTER MTB

Engagement strategy for patients:

Certified Center for Personalized Medicine embedded within the Charité Comprehensive Cancer Center which has patient advocacy groups involved within a patient advisory board

Samples and data flow

General workflows of both samples and data for the NGS analysis

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

Comprehensive analyses are performed via our pathology department for solid tumors and via Labor Berlin for liquid samples (hematological tumors, liquid biopsies). Sequencing for panels is done on routine platforms, genome-wide analyses (WGS, RNA-seq) are done via our central sequencing core. Raw data analysis will be performed within the pathology / Labor Berlin bioinformatics teams. In addition, within our extended network of National Centers of Tumor Diseases (NCTs) we enroll patients into the NCT MASTER Program (<https://www.nct-heidelberg.de/forschung/molecular-stratification/master.html>), which is also linked to the interdisciplinary EURAT (Ethical and Legal Aspects of Whole Genome Sequencing) initiative, which addresses normative questions and aims to develop an ethically and legally informed practice for genomic research. Data will be stored on local Charité / Labor Berlin servers. Standard pipelines are used for data analysis.

Reporting of alterations

Somatic and germline alterations reporting in MTB conclusions

Data interpretation is done both using commercial products such as MH Guide supporting clinical decision making (<https://www.molecularhealth.com/solutions/mh-guide/>), as well as in-house tools and expert team evaluations. Furthermore, within the NCT MASTER program there are also joint weekly discussion of patients entered into the program. Furthermore, there will be a clinical trial match team that looks for available treatment options for the patients both locally, within the extended NCT network and Germany-wide.

MTB endpoints and follow-up

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Synthetic description of the endpoints :

Adherence to MTB decision, inclusion into innovative trials, response to experimental therapy

Endpoint categories (please check the following endpoints when relevant to your MTB) :

Endpoint category	Endpoint subcategory	MTB endpoints (check when relevant)	Details
Patient/Healthcare professionals	Access to high throughput molecular screening	x	
	Outcome	x	
	Access to innovative drugs/trials	x	
	Patient-reported experience measures	x	
Healthcare providers and administrative	MTB activity	x	
	Process (workflows and communication)	x	
Economic impact	Medico-economic evaluation	x	

If applicable, which decision support tool (DST) does the MTB use?

(eg: OncoKDM, Navify, QCI Interpret, SeqOne, etc)

MH Guide (<https://www.molecularhealth.com/solutions/mh-guide/>)

MTB ORGANIZATION

Institution	University Cancer Center Schleswig-Holstein (UCCSH).
Country	Germany
Participants to this form	Prof. Dr. Nikolas von Bubnoff
Type of MTB	Cancers progressing after standard treatment and those lacking standard-of-care treatment options.

General description of MTB

Objectives, frequency, participants and roles, link to national initiatives...

Objectives: With the aim of therapeutic intervention, the molecular Tumor board (MTB) pursues the goal of optimizing the diagnosis and therapy of patients with rare or advanced cancers, lacking guideline-based therapeutic options at the University Medical Center Schleswig-Holstein (UKSH) and in the region.

The University Cancer Center Schleswig-Holstein (UCCSH) is a merger of cancer research institutions of the University Medical Center Schleswig-Holstein (UKSH), in Kiel and Lübeck and supported by the Christian-Albrechts-Universität Kiel and the Universität zu Lübeck. As the leading local cancer center in Schleswig-Holstein and beyond, the UCCSH offers cancer patients interdisciplinary care at the highest level, including state-of-the-art diagnostic workup, precision oncology treatment and the opportunity to receive innovative drugs within clinical trials.

The establishment of an MTB pursues the goal of optimizing the diagnosis and therapy of cancer patients (solid and haematological) at the UKSH and in the region. The MTB complements the work of 26 entity-specific tumour conferences established at both campuses.

Participants & Responsibilities:

The MTB is headed by:

- Prof. Dr. rer. nat. Jutta Kirfel, Institute for Pathology, UCCSH.
 - Prof. Dr. rer. nat. Hauke Busch, Medical Systems Biology Group, Institute for Experimental Dermatology, UCCSH.
 - Dr. med. Lorenz Bastian, Clinic for Inner Medicine II, Haematology and Oncology, UCCSH.
 - Prof. Dr. med. Cyrus Khandanpour, Clinic for Haematology and Oncology, UCCSH.
- Prof. Dr. med. Nikolas von Bubnoff, Clinic for Haematology and Oncology, UCCSH.

MTB responsible persons (clinical):

- Dr. med. Lorenz Bastian, Clinic for Inner Medicine II, Haematology and Oncology, UCCSH.
- PD Dr. med. Niklas Gebauer, Clinic for Haematology and Oncology, UCCSH.
- Prof. Dr. med. Cyrus Khandanpour, Clinic for Haematology and Oncology, UCCSH.
- Prof. Dr. med. Nikolas von Bubnoff, Clinic for Haematology and Oncology, UCCSH.

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External physicians can submit cases and participate in tumor board discussions.

Other responsible people for MTB:

Data Analysis: Dr. re. nat. Anke Fähnrich, Medical Systems Biology Group, Lübeck Institute for Experimental Dermatology, UKSH, Campus Lübeck.

MTB coordinator: Dr. rer. nat. Stephanie Fliedner, University Medical Center Schleswig-Holstein, UKSH

Frequency:

Cycle: Bi-weekly, Fridays at 1:30 p.m. in person and virtual.

Contact & links:

Further information is accessible via:

<https://www.uksh.de/uccsh/>

<https://www.uksh.de/uccsh/%C3%84rzte/Pr%C3%A4zisionsonkologie.html>

mtb.uccsh@uksh.de

Engagement strategy for patients: NA

A patient information document has been circulated to oncologists in the region. Patient referral is via their treating physicians, usually following confirmation by an interdisciplinary tumor conference.

Selection of patient's cases discussed in MTB

Selection criteria, number of cases discussed per MTB

Strict inclusion/exclusion criteria are not defined. A presentation in the MTB is recommended for patients:

- with advanced cancer.
- progressing after standard therapy.
- without a promising treatment option.
- with a rare entity/ molecular pathological profile.
- with unusual clinical courses.
- who are suitable for experimental therapy.

Entity-specific institutional "Inclusion recommendations for the MTB" developed with entity experts have been established. Patient selection is based on interdisciplinary tumor conference recommendations or external referrals. 10-35 cases are discussed in a bi-weekly MTB meeting. Overall, 1531 cases were discussed to date and a total of 261 cases were discussed in 2022.

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Samples and data flow

General workflows of both samples and data for the NGS analysis

A cancer patient's case is presented by the attending cancer specialist. The MTB team comprises specialists from oncology, pathology, systems medicine, clinical genetics, molecular biology, pharmacology, and entity experts from specific departments. External cooperation partners register the cases using the registration form in accordance with the "SOP presentation of external patients in a tumour conference".

The pathology department checks for suitable patient material availability (most recent preferred). The MTB coordination checks for the existence of germline controls and consent declarations. If necessary, a request for the transmission of externally available material is initiated. Detailed documentation of the patient history, lines of treatment, response to treatments, available material and diagnostic tests already performed are documented in the hospital information system ORBIS. A diagnostic recommendation is discussed by an interdisciplinary expert group on a case-by-case basis. The MTB coordination will order the respective molecular diagnostics at the department of pathology, initiating the implementation and reporting of molecular diagnostics. If the available material fails the quality standards, direct feedback is sent to the MTB administration (**Fig 1**).

Figure 1: Overview of the molecular tumour board decision-making process

Raw data from sequencing is transferred to systems biology and evaluated using extensive bioinformatic workup to create a diagnostic report. Recommendations are based on extensive research in available databases, and literature to evaluate the significance of specific variants, therapy options and possible participation in clinical trials (**Fig 2**). Each recommendation is reported with an evidence level according to the National Centre for Tumour Diseases (NCT)/ German Consortium for Translational Cancer Research (DKTK) classification and prioritized when possible.

After the presentation of the relevant findings on a patient case, the treating physician discusses possible diagnostic and/or therapeutic procedures with the patient.

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Figure 2: Workflow of diagnostic procedures, data analysis and therapy recommendation.

Reporting of alterations

Somatic and germline alterations reporting in MTB conclusions

The patient gives consent to evaluate genetic alterations in a defined set of oncogenes and other disease related genes at the germline level. Identified alterations in these actionable genes are evaluated by a human geneticist for relevance. The selection of the genes examined is based on the current list of the American College of Medical Genomics (PMID: 34012068) and the list of actionable genes from OncoKB. Beyond that, no further evaluation of the germline data takes place. If a relevant alteration in the germline is identified, genetic counselling is offered.

At the somatic level, a list of SNVs and InDels, along with the systems biology report and aligned raw data, is stored in binary format (BAM) in a shared location (by pathology, systems biology and human genetics), and the molecular pathology department is informed. For this, two workflows are used for whole exome sequencing analysis: MIRACUM-Pipe (AG-Boerries/MIRACUM-Pipe: v4.0.0, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7468056>) and a GATK workflow for somatic mutations. Additionally, Strelka2 (v2.9.2; 10.1038/s41592-018-0051-x) is used to call somatic variants following the best practices for somatic calling (including MANTA v1.6.0) in the calling procedure.

- The MIRACUM-Pipe trims the fastq input files using Trimmomatic (Bolger et al., 2014), determining the quality before and after using FastQC (Andrews et al., 2010). Initial alignment is done using bwa-mem2 (Vasimuddin et al., 2019), which is used for subsequent steps of statistics, sorting, duplicate removal, and indexing. To correct mapping errors, indel realignment is performed using GATK (10.1101/gr.107524.110), followed by fixing the mate pairs with Picard tools and GATKs workflow for base quality score recalibration. Variants are called using VarScan2 (Koboldt et al., 2012) and annotated with ANNOVAR (Wang et al., 2012).
- Copy numbers are evaluated through ControlFREEC (Boeva et al., 2012).
- For additional biomarkers, a combination of Sequenza (Favero et al., 2015) and scarHRD (Sztupinszki et al., 2018) is used for a score of homologous recombination deficiency (HRD), while MSIsensor-pro (Jia et al., 2020) provides data for microsatellite instability. Apart from microsatellite (MSI) status and HRD score, we calculated the *BRCAness* score (cut-off $\geq 20\%$; Hübschmann et al., 2022).

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- All variants are annotated using Variant Effect Predictor (VEP v105-GRCh37). Integration of variant calling results of VarScan2 (MIRACUM-Pipe), Mutect2, and Strelka2 (both GATK based workflow) is automatically done after completion of both workflows. For both workflows only nonsynonymous mutations detected with a variant allele frequency > 5% and listed with a minor allele frequency < 0.1% by the Exome Aggregation Consortium or gnomAD are reported. Single nucleotide variations are classified according to ClinVar, COSMIC, dbSNP, TARGET db, drug-gene interaction, and CADD (v1.6; Rentzch et al., 2021) and DANN.

RNA-seq data are first trimmed using fastp and mapped to GRCh38 using STARfusion (v1.11.0) to identify gene fusions. Additionally, FusionCatcher (v1.33, Satalan et al., 2014) and arriba (v2.3.0, Uhrig et al., 2021) are used to predict gene fusions. Gene expression profiles are retrieved using kallisto v0.46.1 (Bray et. al., 2016).

MTB endpoints and follow-up

Clinical endpoints, including overall survival (OS) and progression free survival (PFS) are documented through regular contact with the treating physicians. Besides the diagnostic turnaround time, as a valuable parameter for clinical feasibility, overall recommendation rate, type of recommendation (recruitment into clinical trials, single-agent and/or combination treatments, either approved or off-label) are included in the continuous read-out of the MTB. In addition, the implementation rate is monitored. In cases where the recommendation is realized, best clinical and/or radiological response as well as PFS-ratio in comparison with the last guideline-adherent therapy is assessed. Endpoints relevant to the performance of the MTB are documented, as described (Hoefflin R et al., 2018, Horak P et al., 2021). Workflow-performance, recruitment through organ-specific boards and outcome-parameters are closely monitored and addressed in regularly scheduled interdisciplinary task-force meetings. Observations of particular interest are published in the format of molecularly informed case reports or series (Witte HM et al., 2023).

Endpoint categories (*please check the following endpoints when relevant to your MTB*) :

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Endpoint category	Endpoint subcategory	MTB endpoints (check when relevant)	Details
Patient/Healthcare professionals	Access to high throughput molecular screening	X	
	Outcome	X	OS and PFS within specific projects
	Access to innovative drugs/trials	X	Treatment propositions and inclusions into clinical trials
	Patient-reported experience measures	In preparation	NA
Healthcare providers and administrative	MTB activity	X	-Number of patients discussed in the MTB - Centralized screening for specific clinical trials - Scientific publications if applicable
	Process (workflows and communication)	X	Synthesis of the difficulties encountered and proposal of improvements
Economic impact	Medico-economic evaluation	NA	

If applicable, which decision support tool (DST) does the MTB use?

(eg: OncoKDM, Navify, QCI Interpret, SeqOne, etc)

Analyzed sequencing data is integrated with clinical information necessary for decision-making on cBioPortal (Memorial Sloan Kettering). In preparation for the molecular Tumour board, embedded databases are utilized. During the MTB, prioritized recommendations are documented in cBioPortal and transferred back to the clinical information system.

MTB ORGANIZATION

Institution	IRCCS National Cancer Institute Regina Elena (IRE), IFO
Country	Rome, Italy
Participants to this form	Gennaro Ciliberto, Patrizio Giacomini, Fabio Valenti
Type of MTB	MTB, real-world, metastatic setting, no standard therapy option

General description of MTB

Objectives, frequency, participants and multidisciplinary roles (medical, scientist, management and administrative if relevant), link to national initiatives, engagement strategy for patients ...

Objectives: The MTB-IRE was established by Scientific Director Prof. Gennaro Ciliberto and his collaborators in July 2018, by deliberation No. 468 dated 19-06-2018. Primary aim: identify actionable alterations outside approved indications (mainly OncoKB levels 3A/B). Secondary aim: assignment of non-standard therapy and evaluation of clinical outcome. Ex-post, not pre-planned analyses include comparison with routine genomic profiling, patient tracking from routine to MTB settings, barrier to treatment, etc

Frequency: every 15 days, virtual attendance.

Each meeting addresses:

- Discussion of new clinical cases;
- Updates of previously discussed cases that have received a recommendation from the MTB-IRE;
- Cases routinely sequenced: analysis of non-SoC indications for future re-use.

Participants & Responsibilities (including administrative & medical management profiles if relevant) :

- Scientific Coordinator: Gennaro Ciliberto, MD

Active members and main attendants: oncologists, molecular biologists/biotechnologists, pathologists, biostatisticians and bioinformaticians, a hospital pharmacist, a delegate from the Institutional Biobank, the Scientific Secretary and an executive Secretary. Hematologists, endocrinologist-oncologists, a medical geneticist, interventional radiologists and radiotherapists, surgeons, patient advocacy delegates, nurses, data managers and representatives of the local health governance are invited to participate depending on the topics to be addressed, as per the MTB agenda distributed at least 24 h in advance. Two discussants (clinical and molecular) are appointed for each MTB case.

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Contact & links: gennaro.ciliberto@ifo.it

<https://www.ifo.it/ricerca/direzione-scientifica-ire/molecular-tumor-board-mtb-ire/>

<https://ricerca.ifo.it/ire-research/ire-excellences/molecular-tumor-board-mtb/>

The web site includes materials for the layman, clips, and specific information for professionals.

Link to national and multi-center initiatives:

The MTB-IRE has activated separate official agreements with 7 cancer centers in the greater Rome area (regione Lazio) The regional network has been officially endorsed as a clinical study and approved by the Ethical Committee. The MTB-IRE has also conducted a survey among the MTBs of other institutions belonging to the network of Alliance Against Cancer (ACC) in Italy. This system aims to spread "best practices" and to create collaborations and shared knowledge among oncology-oriented institutions, with the possibility of sharing not only medical knowledge but also technological set-up.

Engagement strategy for patients:

Patients are referred by the oncologist or a medical doctor.

Enrolment criteria:

(a) any neoplastic condition, (b) >18 yr, (c) no standard treatment options, (d) available tumor tissue and/or circulating tumor DNA (tDNA and/or ctDNA), and (e) Performance Status (PS) \leq 2.

(b) Exclusion, none except refusal to sign informed consent

Samples and data flow

General workflows of both samples and data for the NGS analysis

Between 1 and 3 cases per single session are discussed. Patients are afferent to the Regina Elena Institute or its affiliated centers. Patients are referred for discussion to the MTB by clinical oncologists after previous assessment at their relevant DMTs. Patients must have failed previous lines of conventional therapy and must have PS 0 or 1. Step 1: informed consent. Step 2: case presentation during the first round of collegial discussion. Step 3: genomic profiling, mostly involving NGS on tDNA and ctDNA, either *de novo* or as a complement to the available genomic profiling. Step 4: joint appointment of two case discussants, providing distinct pieces of expertise, clinical and molecular. Step 5: case review in a second discussion round (typically 15 days later) and MTB recommendations. Step 6: treatment recommendation. Therapy is ultimately decided by the oncologist (usually the clinical discussant) and agreed with the patient.

Each new case presented in the first session by the clinical speaker (usually an oncologist) is discussed in a multidisciplinary manner to determine what molecular investigations are needed. At this point,

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identification of the sample to be analyzed (tissue and/or blood) is attempted and then which study method to apply for analysis (NGS with ThermoFischer panels, Illumina, Foundation or WGS, WES and RNAseq). After this first phase of molecular analysis, usually performed over the next 15 days, the molecular and clinical speaker, supported by a bioinformatician, reports the case in the next session during which the results obtained are discussed. Specifically, the molecular data obtained are analyzed and discussed, focusing on any activating mutations (EGFR, KRAS, BRAF, etc.), rearrangements (EGFR, ALK ROS1, RET, etc.) and other mutational events, and, also referring to data already in the literature, and after careful evaluation of costs/benefits, the MTB issues a recommendation. The latter directs the patient to a therapeutic solution and/or inclusion in a clinical trial based on a specific molecular alteration.

Reporting of alterations

Somatic and germline alterations reporting in MTB conclusions

Somatic: as per international databases, such as ESCAt and OncoKB. Recommendations/indications are annotated in a local database of the MTB-IRE in a specific patient record.

Germ line: handled as incidental finding+gs and referred to our heredofamilial cancer unit

MTB endpoints and follow-up

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Synthetic description of the endpoints :

Endpoint categories (please check the following endpoints when relevant to your MTB) :

Descriptive statistics: PFS, TTP, treatment duration, Von Hoff etc

Endpoint category	Endpoint subcategory	MTB endpoints (check when relevant)	Details
Patient/Healthcare professionals	Access to high throughput molecular screening	X	Particularly for inpatient-outpatient comparisons
	Outcome	X	See above
	Access to innovative drugs/trials	X	Limited to OncoKB levels 3A/B, rarely level 4
	Patient-reported experience measures	x	A narrative description is being curated by Ciliberto and Giacomini. Patient advocacy involved
Healthcare providers and administrative	MTB activity	no	unclear
	Process (workflows and communication)	X	See website
Economic impact	Medico-economic evaluation	no	Not formally carried out

If applicable, which decision support tool (DST) does the MTB use?

(eg: OncoKDM, Navify, QCI Interpret, SeqOne, etc)

OncoKB and the commercial Thermofisher/ Life Technologies: Oncomine Knowledgebase Reporter; OKR, linking to active clinical trials

MTB ORGANIZATION

Institution	AP-HP
Country	France
Participants to this form	Raphael Itzykson, Emmanuelle Clappier, William Plas
Type of MTB	National MTB for relapsed/refractory acute leukemias

General description of MTB

Objectives, frequency, participants and multidisciplinary roles (medical, scientist, management and administrative if relevant), link to national initiatives, engagement strategy for patients ...

Objectives: The objective of the national RCP "LA en rechute" is to organize the management of patients with relapsed/refractory acute lymphoblastic and acute myeloid leukemia.

The national MTB is part of the national initiative Plan France Médecine Génomique (PFMG) 2025 (<https://pfmtg2025.aviesan.fr/>) to validate indications for additional examinations and in particular the possibility of pan-genomic examinations. It also constitutes discussion on the genomic results delivered by PFMG labs, as well as ex vivo drug testing performed on the NEXT-AML and ALL-TARGET platforms for AML and T-ALL respectively.

Participants & Responsibilities (including administrative & medical management profiles if relevant) :

Medical coordinators:

- Pr Raphael Itzykson (AML)
- Pr Emmanuelle Clappier (B-ALL)
- Pr Philippe Rousselot (T-ALL)
- Pr Sophie Park (medical coordinator for Auragen centers)

Biological coordinators:

- Pr Emmanuelle Clappier (SeqOIA)
- Pr Pascale Flandrin-Gesta (AURAGEN)
- Dr Ludovic Lhermitte (ALL-TARGET drug testing)
- Pr Raphael Itzykson (NEXT-AML drug testing)

The MTB brings together hematologists with complementary skills in clinical management, genomic data analysis and interpretation, and functional precision medicine.

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

A coordination team at Hôpital Saint-Louis, APHP, is in charge of the MTB preparation and transcription.

The MTB is a meeting opened to all national hospitals, facilities, and all experts referring a patient with relapsed or refractory ALL or AML.

It is recommended that the prescribing physician be present at the national MTB.

The prescribing physician is the doctor who will report the results to the patient. He/she agrees to :

- To complete the national MTB form (patient registration information).
- Provide clinical, morphology, cytogenetic and molecular biology reports.
- Give the patient the information on the reuse of data and samples for research purposes and keep proof of this information in the medical file.

Contact & links:

- Candice Pratlong (Candice.pratlong@aphp.fr) to register a case.
- Cytometrie.thema@gmail.com for NEXT-AML drug testing.
- Ludovic Lhermitte (ludovic.lhermitte@aphp.fr) for ALL-TARGET drug testing.
- William Plas (William.plas@aphp.fr) for SeqOIA centers.

Frequency: Every other Thursday at 3 pm via Zoom.

<https://u-paris.zoom.us/j/87990639077?pwd=N05vS1JIaE50OGhZMGdvRXhXTWF6QT09>

Engagement strategy for patients: NA

Selection patients cases discussed in MTB

Selection criteria, number of cases discussed per MTB

From 1 to 10 cases are discussed per MTB.

Any patient with relapsed or refractory AML or ALL eligible for active therapies, including after allogeneic hematopoietic cell transplantation, can be registered. This preindication is limited to new incident cases.

Samples and data flow

General workflows of both samples and data for the NGS analysis

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

The different steps of the National CUP MTB workflow are:

- 1) the referring physician registers the patient for national MTB
- 2) **MTB 1 ("upstream") :**
 - Validation of the indication
 - PFMG 2023 (SeqOIA [<https://laboratoire-seqoia.fr/>] or AURAGEN [<https://www.auragen.fr/>] platform) prescription : WGS, WES and RNAseq
- 3) Medical consultation, signature of consent and samples shipment (tumor and blood) to corresponding sites for extraction and sequencing platform for sequencing
- 4) WES/WGS & RNAseq
- 5) Data integration
- 6) Validation of results and molecular reports
- 7) Optionally, ex vivo drug testing on the NEXT-AML (AML) or ALL-TARGET (T-ALL) platforms.

- 8) **MTB 2 ("downstream"):**
 - Review of the alterations reported by the molecular biologists
 - Refinement of the prognostic assessment, potential diagnostic reassessment, and suggestion of one or several therapeutic options (either based on the newly proposed diagnosis, prognosis, or based on a druggable molecular alteration or functional dependence).

Referring physicians are notified and invited to participate on both MTB 1 and MTB 2.

The MTB 1 & 2 reports are sent by email to the corresponding external referring physician either directly (SeqOIA centers) or through the Auragen coordinators (Auragen centers). For APHP patients, both results and conclusions are also integrated directly into the medical record.

Reporting of alterations

Somatic and germline alterations reporting in MTB conclusions

Synthetic description of the endpoints :

An annual assessment of MTB activity includes:

- Presentation of the number of cases discussed, molecular analyses and treatment proposals
- The following indicators:
 - Proportion of patients with at least one target
 - Proportion of patients referred to an interventional clinical trial,
- Synthesis of the difficulties encountered and proposal of improvements,
- If applicable, scientific publications

MTB endpoints and follow-up

Synthetic description of the endpoints :

Endpoint categories (please check the following endpoints when relevant to your MTB):

Endpoint category	Endpoint subcategory	MTB endpoints (check when relevant)	Details
Patient/Healthcare professionals	Access to high throughput molecular screening	X	Number and type of molecular analyses per year and per tumor type
	Outcome	X	OS and response in patients within specific projects
	Access to innovative drugs/trials	X	Treatment proposals and clinical trial referral
	Patient-reported experience measures		
Healthcare providers and administrative	MTB activity		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of patients discussed in the MTB - Number of centers referring cases - Scientific publications if applicable
	Process (workflows and communication)	X	Synthesis of the difficulties encountered and proposal of improvements
Economic impact	Medico-economic evaluation		

If applicable, which decision support tool (DST) does the MTB use?

(eg: OncoKDM, Navify, QCI Interpret, SeqOne, etc)

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

Target prioritization is partially based on OncoKB.

MTB ORGANIZATION

Institution	Belgium Society of Medical Oncology (BSMO) – PRECISION program
Country	Belgium
Participants to this form	Philippe Aftimos, Brigitte Maes
Type of MTB	“National” MTB discussing metastatic solid tumors patient cases

General description of MTB

Objectives, frequency, participants and multidisciplinary roles (medical, scientist, management and administrative if relevant), link to national initiatives, engagement strategy for patients ...

Objectives:

- Identify patients with molecular alterations that can be targeted with standard of care or in genotype-driven clinical trials
- Build and share knowledge
- Facilitate patient referral between centers

Participants & Responsibilities (including administrative & medical management profiles if relevant) :

- 1 project manager
- Specialists (medical oncologists, gastro-enterologists, gynecologists, pulmonologists), molecular pathologists, geneticists, pathologists, study coordinators from all academic and non-academic centers in Belgium.

Contact & links:

Philippe Aftimos: philippe.aftimos@bordet.be

Brigitte Maes : brigitte.maes@jessazh.be

Virtual meeting link: https://teams.microsoft.com/l/meetup-join/19%3ameeting_ODM0YjliZDI0MmYyZi00MDFkLTg3ZWUtNmYwZWQyOWI0ODYy%40thread.v2/0?context=%7b%22Tid%22%3a%223ea7d703-c55a-4121-ba9b-96825471f7d0%22%2c%22Oid%22%3a%220918601f-810c-450e-bd5b-66be5ba48add%22%7d

Frequency: every Friday at 2 PM

The “national” MTB was created within the PRECISION Belgium initiative (doi: 10.1016/j.esmoop.2022.100524) and is open to anyone involved in the care of patients with cancer. All solid tumor cases with comprehensive genomic profiling are eligible to be discussed.

Source of cases:

- GeNeo: ClincialTrials.gov: NCT04641676
- BALLETT: ClincialTrials.gov: NCT05058937

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- GeNeo 2: TBC

Tests:

- GeNeo: FoundationOne CDx, FoundationOne Liquid CDx, FoundationOne Heme (rare tumors)
- BALLETT: Illumina TruSight Oncology 500

Samples and data flow

General workflows of both samples and data for the NGS analysis

- GeNeo: central testing at Foundation Medicine
- BALLETT: local testing with the Trusight Oncology 500 (Illumina) by a consortium of 9 NGS laboratories, according to a predefined run-schedule (weekly alternating between participating laboratories)

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Reporting of alterations

Somatic and germline alterations reporting in MTB conclusions

GeNeo: standard FMI reporting (PDF). A summary of the FMI results is transferred to a report in Word. In that report also the treatment recommendations are listed, indicating also the order of priority.

BALLETT:

- Raw sequencing data files are sent to the local site where the patient was recruited.
- SNV's and small indels are biologically classified according to the Belgian ComPerMed guidelines by the local NGS laboratory.
- Amplifications and fusions, TMB values, MSI and HRD results are also retrieved from the TSO500 data analysis pipeline by the local NGS laboratories.
- All alterations are clinically classified according to Li et al (ASCO/CAP/AMP; TierIA, B; Tier IIC, D).
- All results, including classifications, are registered by the local sites in the patient record in Castor (eCRF).
- Proposals for treatment recommendations are also registered by local sites in the eCRF and discussed during the pre-MTB NGS lab meeting (Friday at 9 am), where mainly classification of variants is discussed and agreed upon.
- During the MTB, a custom-designed app, that extracts data from Castor, is used for:
 - o Visualization and presentation of the clinical and molecular data to the MTB members (in MS Teams)
 - o Linking to gene-drug match database
 - o Discussing the proposed treatment recommendations by linking to relevant websites (eg. ClinicalTrials.gov)
 - o Discussing, finalizing and prioritizing treatment recommendations (eg. Approved treatments, clinical trials, medical need programs, off-label drug use)
- The MTB report, including molecular findings and treatment recommendations, is downloaded from the custom BALLETT app in PDF and sent to the treating physician.

GeNeo and BALLETT:

- Regarding germline alterations, MTB only reports suspicion of germline alteration based on the results of the somatic analysis. If a germline alteration is suspected, the MTB recommend to the physician to organize a genetic consultation for the patient and germline genetic testing, outside of the MTB.
- The MTB reports are archived locally as well as in a national database (Health Data, Sciensano).

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

MTB endpoints and follow-up

Synthetic description of the endpoints :

- Number/prevalence of clinically significant alterations; overall and per tumor type
- Number of treatment recommendations per type; per tumor type
- Patient journey, eg. TATs, CGP failure, ...
- Costs
- Follow-up data registered:
 - Whether the treatment recommendation was followed or not
 - If not, the reason why not
 - Progression free survival (PFS) for calculation of PFS-ratio (in BALLETT, not in GeNeo)

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

Endpoint categories (please check the following endpoints when relevant to your MTB) :

Endpoint category	Endpoint subcategory	MTB endpoints (check when relevant)	Details
Patient/Healthcare professionals	Access to high throughput molecular screening	x	
	Outcome	x	PRECISION 1 database
	Access to innovative drugs/trials	x	Reasons for deviations from the recommendation are recorded.
	Patient-reported experience measures		
Healthcare providers and administrative	MTB activity	x	Discussions with the health authorities towards reimbursement.
	Process (workflows and communication)	x	-TAT -Synthesis of the difficulties encountered and proposal of improvements.
Economic impact	Medico-economic evaluation	x	Discussion with Health Care department and decision-makers based on the final analysis report of the study.

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If applicable, which decision support tool (DST) does the MTB use?

(eg: OncoKDM, Navify, QCI Interpret, SeqOne, etc)

- GeNeo : FMI standard procedures (FMI PDF report available for (preparation of) MTB), NAVIFY Tumor Board for case discussion during MTB (Roche)
- BALLETT :
 - o Custom-designed BALLETT-app during MTB
 - o OncoKDM (OncoDNA) and CGW (PierianDx/Velsera) during MTB preparation by local NGS labs

MTB ORGANIZATION

Institution	CENTRE ANTOINE LACASSAGNE
Country	FRANCE
Participants to this form	
Type of MTB	PACA EST MTB

General description of MTB

Objectives, frequency, participants and multidisciplinary roles (medical, scientist, management and administrative if relevant), link to national initiatives, engagement strategy for patients ...

Objectives:

The objective of the "RTB moléculaire" is to propose early phases clinical trials and/or the prescription of new treatments, which are not routinely available, to patients who are in treatment failure.

All tumoral pathologies refractory to conventional treatments or for which there is no therapeutic standard (rare cancers) are included.

This MTB contributes to advance personalized medicine and constitutes a priority objective of the medical-scientific project (PMS) of the CAL, in harmony with the Cancer Plan 3 and the objectives of the PMS of UNICANCER.

Participants & Responsibilities (including administrative & medical management profiles if relevant) :

Medical coordinators :

- Dr Esmâ SAADA BOUZID (Oncologist)
- Dr Bérangère DADONE-MONTAUDIÉ (Pathologist)

The molecular analyses prescribed following the PACA EST MTB are carried out via the hospital platform for molecular genetics of cancers in the PACA-Est region, which includes various laboratories cooperating with each other. This common platform includes several laboratories whose members are systematically invited to the PACA EST MTB.

Dr François PETIT (Biologist)

Dr Nathalie Ebran (Biologist)

Ilaria DI MAURIO (Hospital Engineer)

Raihane BEN ABDELJELIL (CRA)

Aline BARSOTTI (Technician)

Dr Valérie DURANTON-TANNEUR (Biologist)

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Dr Marie-Christine ETIENNE-GRIMALDI (Biologist, Pharm D)

The MTB is headed by a medical coordinator and brings together several experts with complementary skills: oncologists, pathologists, managers of molecular analysis platforms, and biologists.

The MTB relies on the presence of at least one oncologist, a pathologist, a biologist, and the CRA who is in charge of the MTB preparation and transcription.

Contact & links:

Medical coordinator : esma.saad-bouزيد@nice.unicancer.fr

CRA : 04.92.03.14.63 / Raihane.BENABDELJELIL@nice.unicancer.fr

Frequence: Once a week. Each Thursday at 11am in a meeting room.

Engagement strategy for patients: NA

Selection patients cases discussed in MTB

Selection criteria, number of cases discussed per MTB

From 1 to 25 cases are discussed per MTB.

Any adult patient with advanced cancer, a performance status (PS) equal to or less than 1, and who has not multiple cancers simultaneously.

Samples and data flow

General workflows of both samples and data for the NGS analysis

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

Figure 1: PACA EST MTB validation workflow

Figure 2 : REPOS NETWORK details

See attached files. The different steps of the PACA EST MTB workflow are:

- 1) The CRA registers the patient for PACA EST MTB.
- 2) **MTB 1 :**
 - Verification of eligibility criteria
 - Proposal of molecular analyses
 - PFMG 2025 (AURAGEN [<https://www.auragen.fr/>] platform) prescription : WGS, WES and RNAseq
- 3) Medical consultation, signature of consent and samples shipment (tumor and blood) to corresponding sites for extraction and sequencing platform for sequencing
- 4) WES/WGS & RNAseq **OR** NGS, MSI, RNAseq, SNParray, GREAT/HRR, etc.
- 5) Data integration
- 6) Validation of results and molecular reports
- 7) **MTB 2 :**
 - Review of the alterations reported by the molecular biologists
 - Proposition of an early phases clinical trials and/or the prescription of new treatments which are not routinely available.

Referring oncologists are notified and invited to participate on both MTB 1 and MTB 2.

The MTB 2 conclusions and the molecular results are send by email to the corresponding external referring physician. For CAL patients, both results and conclusions are also integrated directly into the medical record (CLINICOM + eRCP + Data Base).

Reporting of alterations

Somatic and germline alterations reporting in MTB conclusions

Somatic alterations are listed in a NGS report which is done by the molecular biologists and discussed in MTB. The classification allows to classify variants according to 5 different classes :

Classification des variants selon UNCseq (Hayes and Kim, J Clin Invest, 2015, PMID:25642706) :

- **Classe 5** : *variant actionnable*
 - *variant avec une AMM dans la pathologie*
 - *variant avec une AMM dans une autre pathologie*
 - *variant pour lequel il existe des thérapies ciblées en essais cliniques*
 - *variant pour lequel il existe des données précliniques*
 - *variant à signification pronostique*
- **Classe 4** : *variant sans effet théranostique connu mais avec un effet potentiel activateur (oncogène) ou délétère (gène suppresseur)*
- **Classe 3** : *variant sans effet connu dans la littérature ; des données de modélisation peuvent orienter vers un effet de la mutation*
- **Classe 2** : *variant potentiellement neutre, non rapporté dans le compte-rendu*
- **Classe 1** : *variant connu comme un polymorphisme constitutionnel, non rapporté dans le compte-rendu*

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The SNParray carried out in the LGTS allows to generate a summary table of the quantitative genomic anomalies of interest in the context of PACA EST MTB.

Discussions in MTB 2 allows to :

- Validate molecular alterations of interest based on PFMG2025 analyses (WES/WGS/RNAseq) or molecular analyses carried out by the LOP, LGTS and/or LPCE
- Discuss results of complementary analyses requested during MTB 1 (anatomopathological, clinical or molecular).
- If possible orientation towards clinical trials or off-label treatment. (*)

(*) Several types of conclusions are possible:

- no specific proposal
- no trial targeting this mutation
- proposal for inclusion in a clinical trial
- proposal for off-label treatment
- indication of a new biopsy

Both molecular reports and MTB conclusions are send to the referral physicians by email.

MTB endpoints and follow-up

Endpoint categories *(please check the following endpoints when relevant to your MTB):*

Endpoint category	Endpoint subcategory	MTB endpoints <i>(check when relevant)</i>	Details
Patient/Healthcare professionals	Access to high throughput molecular screening	X	
	Outcome		
	Access to innovative drugs/trials	X	clinical trials or off-label treatment
	Patient-reported experience measures		
Healthcare providers and administrative	MTB activity	X	
	Process (workflows and communication)	X	
Economic impact	Medico-economic evaluation		

Synthetic description of the endpoints :

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These indicators are updated semi-annually :

- Quorum, frequency
- Number of cases submitted monthly :
 - o Centre Antoine Lacassagne (CAL) patients
 - o CHU NICE patients
 - o External patients
- Compliance with PACA EST MTB decisions :
 - o Number of cases where the MTB decision was followed
 - o Number of cases for which another therapeutic alternative was chosen.
 - o Number of cases included in a clinical trial

A shared database, hosted and managed by the Department of Epidemiology, Biostatistics and Health Data of the CAL (Ennov Clinical) allows to evaluate and to use PACA EST MTB datas. Each user has secure access with rights defined according to their profile (administrator, user, reader, etc.).

This database allows to:

- Record the cases presented during these MTB with the decision of the MTB
- Identify all analyses and anomalies found.

This database was the subject of a declaration to the CNIL by the Direction de la Recherche Clinique et Innovation of the Centre Antoine Lacassagne.

If applicable, which decision support tool (DST) does the MTB use?

(eg: OncoKDM, Navify, QCI Interpret, SeqOne, etc)

Figure 1: PACA EST MTB validation workflow

Figure 2 : REPOS NETWORK details

MTB ORGANIZATION

Institution	Assistance Publique Hôpitaux de Paris
Country	France
Participants to this form	Pierre Laurent-Puig; Jacques Cadranel; Anne-Paule Gimenez-Roqueplo; Camille Tlemsani
Type of MTB	Institutional MTB for rare cancers and cancer patients in therapeutic failure

General description of MTB

Objectives, frequency, participants and multidisciplinary roles (medical, scientist, management and administrative if relevant), link to national initiatives, engagement strategy for patients ...

Objectives: The objective of this institutional MTB is to organize, at the level of the 39 university hospitals participating to the Assistance Publique Hopitaux de Paris (APHP) network, the management of patients with a rare cancer and patients with a non hematological solid tumor in therapeutic failure. This MTB is part of the national initiative Plan France Médecine Génomique 2025 (PFMG 2025) (<https://pfmq2025.aviesan.fr/>) which aims to validate the indication of a whole genome (WGS), exome (WES), and transcriptome (WTS) for such patients (pre indications) in clinical routine in order to propose, based on the genomic results, the best therapeutic strategy.

Participants & Responsibilities (including administrative & medical management profiles if relevant) :

Medical coordinators

Pr. Pierre Laurent-Puig (Oncologist, European Georges Pompidou Hospital)

Pr. Jacques Cadranel (Pneumologist/Thoracic oncologist, Tenon Hospital)

Pr. Anne Paule Gimenez-Roqueplo (Geneticist, European Georges Pompidou Hospital)

Dr. Camille Tlemsani (Oncologist, Cochin Hospital)

Administrative coordinator (MTB manager)

Mandjula Deville (European Georges Pompidou Hospital)

Experts committee

Dr. Laetitia Marisa (Bioinformatician, European Georges Pompidou Hospital), Pr. Nelly Burnichon (Geneticist, European Georges Pompidou Hospital); Pr. Helene Blons (Biochemist, European Georges Pompidou Hospital); Pr. Karen Leroy (Oncologist, European Georges Pompidou Hospital), Dr. Jeanne Netter (Gastroenterologist, European Georges Pompidou), Pr. Jerome Alexandre (Oncologist, Cochin Hospital); Dr Anne Jouinot (Oncologist, Cochin hospital); Dr. Audrey Lupo (Pathologist, Cochin Hospital), Pr. Eric Pasmant (Geneticist, Cochin Hospital), Pr. Guillem Bousquet (Oncologist, Avicenne Hospital), Pr. Jean-Charles Nault (Hepatologist, Avicenne Hospital), Pr. Marc Sanson (Neurologist, Pitié-Salpêtrière Hospital), Dr. Mehdi Touat (Neurologist Pitié-Salpêtrière Hospital), Dr. Vincent Fallet (Pneumologist/Thoracic oncologist, Tenon Hospital), Dr. Patrick Benusiglio (Geneticist, Tenon Hospital)

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

The MTB is headed by one of the medical coordinator and brings together several experts with complementary skills: oncologists, pathologists, geneticists, managers of molecular analysis platforms, bio-informaticians and molecular biologists. The MTB relies on the presence of at least one oncologist, one molecular biologist, one bioinformatician and the RCP project manager.

The coordination team oversees the MTB preparation and transcription.

The medical coordinator, among the 4 accredited medical coordinators, validates:

- The indication and prescription of molecular analyses for a given patient
- The MTB reports and conclusions and orientation towards clinical trials or specific treatments

The MTB is a meeting opened to all participating hospitals from the APHP Network, and all experts referring a patient with rare cancer or a cancer patient in therapeutic failure situation.

It is recommended that the prescribing physician be present at the MTB.

The prescribing physician is the doctor who will report the results to the patient. He/she agrees to:

- Complete the MTB form (patient registration information).
- Provide anatomopathological and molecular biology reports.
- Give the patient the information on the reuse of data and samples for research purposes and keep proof of this information in the medical file.

Contact & links:

Preparation and retranscription of this MTB is done by Jeanne Netter, Laetitia Marisa and Mandjula Deville under the supervision of one of the medical coordinators.

The email contact is: rcptsseqoia.aphp@aphp.fr

Frequence:

Twice a month, on 2nd and 4th Tuesdays at 5pm. Virtual meeting (Teams)

Engagement strategy for patients: NA

Samples and data flow

General workflows of both samples and data for the NGS analysis

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

From 10 to 40 cases are discussed per MTB

Any cancer patient with therapeutic failure; any patient with a rare cancer at any time of the disease

The workflow is summarized in the figure 1

The different steps of the institutional APHP MTB workflow are:

- 1) The referring physician registers the patient for MTB rare cancer or therapeutic failure
- 2) **Upstream MTB:**
 - Validation of the indication depending of the preindication [<https://pfgm2025.aviesan.fr/professionnels/preindications-et-mise-en-place/cancers-rares/>] and [<https://pfgm2025.aviesan.fr/professionnels/preindications-et-mise-en-place/cancers-avances-en-echec-therapeutique/>]
 - PFMG 2025 (SeqOIA [<https://laboratoire-seqoia.fr/>])prescription : WGS, WES and RNAseq
- 3) Medical consultation, signature of consent and samples shipment (tumor and blood) to corresponding platforms for nucleic acids extraction
- 4) WES/WGS & RNAseq by the SeqOIA (Sequencing, Omics, Information Analysis) platform, which is part of the PFMG 2025
- 5) Data integration by the bioinformatician
- 6) Validation of results and molecular reports by the molecular biologists
- 7) **Downstream MTB:**
 - Review of the genetic alterations reported by the molecular biologists
 - Collective proposition of a diagnosis and/or therapeutic option (either based on the newly proposed diagnostic or based on a druggable molecular alteration)

Referring physicians are notified and invited to participate on both upstream and downstream MTB.

The MTB conclusions and the molecular results are sent by email to the corresponding referring physician.

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

Reporting of alterations

Somatic and germline alterations reporting in MTB conclusions

Somatic alterations are listed in a NGS report which is done by the molecular biologists and discussed in MTB. Somatic alterations reported by the molecular biologists are selected according to different levels of classification:

1. Gene classification as Oncogene or Tumor Suppressor Gene according to OncoKB database, COSMIC database and the literature
2. Variant classification:
 - a. Based on ACMG international classification that includes verification of international databases for variants classification:
 - ESP6500 & gnomAD for incidence in the general population
 - COSMIC, oncoKB & ClinVar for variant pathogenicity of all genes
 - International database for variant pathogenicity of specific genes

The classification allows to classify variants according to 5 different classes: pathogenic; likely pathogenic; variant of uncertain significance; likely benign; benign. The result is then adapted to somatic alterations taking into account the tumoral context (e.g. tumor cellularity, VAF, presence of signatures, LOH, variant expression when RNAseq is available, etc.)

A MSI status, a score HRD, and the description of the mutational signature are also reported. Several signature based on WTS are also reported to better classify the tumor or to orientate the treatment.

Discussions in downstream MTB allows to:

- Validate molecular alterations of interest based on PFMG2025 analyses (WES/WGS/WTS)
- Precise the diagnosis according to the different results
- Establish treatment recommendations for patients and if possible, orientation towards clinical trials

Both molecular reports and MTB conclusions are reported to the electronic file system of the APHP.

Regarding germline alterations, MTB only reports suspicion of germline alteration based on the results of the somatic analysis. If a germline alteration is suspected, the MTB recommends to the physician to organize a genetic consultation for the patient, outside of the MTB.

During this genetic consultation, the oncogeneticist will then either prescribe an additional analysis to confirm the germline alteration, or give to the patient the results of the constitutional DNA (WES/WGS SeqOIA) analysis.

MTB endpoints and follow-up

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

Synthetic description of the endpoints:

A bi-annual assessment of MTB activity includes:

- Presentation of the number of cases discussed, molecular analyses, treatment propositions and inclusions into clinical trials
- The following indicators:
 - Proportion of targetable alterations identified thanks to one the following NGS: WGS, WES, WTS
 - Proportion of patients enrolled in clinical therapeutic trials.
- Synthesis of the difficulties encountered and proposal of improvements, If applicable, scientific publications

Endpoint categories (please check the following endpoints when relevant to your MTB):

Endpoint category	Endpoint subcategory	MTB endpoints	Details
Patient/Healthcare professionals	Access to high throughput molecular screening	X	Number and type of molecular analyses per year and per tumor type
	Outcome	X	report of issue of the therapeutic strategy proposed. Access to the drug: trial, early access program, prescription of authorized drug in other indication; response rate, duration of treatment
	Access to innovative drugs/trials	X	Treatment propositions and inclusions into clinical trials
	Patient-reported experience measures		Should be implemented
Healthcare providers and administrative	MTB activity	X	- Number of patients discussed in the MTB - Scientific publications if applicable
	Process (workflows and communication)	X	Synthesis of the difficulties encountered and proposal of improvements
Economic impact	Medico-economic evaluation		NA

If applicable, which decision support tool (DST) does the MTB use?

(eg: OncoKDM, Navify, QCI Interpret, SeqOne, etc)

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

None

MTB ORGANIZATION

Institution	Institut Curie
Country	France
Participants to this form	Maud Kamal, Célia Dupain
Type of MTB	Local MTB for metastatic cancers in recurrence or progression & rare cancers

General description of MTB

Objectives, frequency, participants and roles, link to national initiatives...

Objectives: The Institut Curie MTB aims to refer patients with metastatic cancer in recurrence or progression, or with a rare cancer, towards a clinical trial with innovative molecules, based on the tumor molecular characterisation.

The Institut Curie MTB is labeled MTB of the national genomic initiative (Plan France Médecine Génomique 2025 - PFMG 2025), as Institut Curie is part of the SeqOIA platform (<https://pfm2025.aviesan.fr/>) located at Broussais Hospital.

Participants & Responsibilities:

- Medical coordinator : Christophe Le Tourneau, MD, PhD,
- Scientific coordinator : Maud Kamal, PhD,
- Referent biologist : Ivan Bièche, PharmD, PhD,
- Referent pathologist : Anne Vincent-Salomon, MD, PhD,
- Referent radiologist : Vincent Servois, MD,
- Project managers : Célia Dupain, PhD and Isabelle Guillou.

Contact email: RCPmolCurieSeqOIA@curie.fr

The MTB is headed by a medical coordinator and brings together several experts with complementary skills: oncologists, radiologists, pathologists, managers of molecular analysis platforms, bio-informaticians and biologists. The MTB relies on the presence of at least one oncologist, a pathologist, a biologist, and the scientific manager or molecular RCP project manager.

A coordination team is in charge of the MTB preparation and transcription

The medical coordinator must be an oncologist who validates :

- The indication and prescription of molecular analyses for a given patient
- MTB reports and conclusions and orientation towards clinical trials

The MTB is a meeting opened to :

- All members of the Institut Curie Hospital.

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

- All hospitals with a regional MTB labeled PFMG 2025 for which the Institut Curie MTB is the Qualifier/Extractor center (Amiens, Caen, Lille, Rouen).
- All facilities in the region (besides AP-HP) that do not have direct access to the PFMG 2025 or to molecular analysis platforms (Foch, IMM, Versailles, etc.)

Frequence: Once a week, on Mondays at 5pm. Virtual meeting (Teams) :

https://teams.microsoft.com/l/meetup-join/19%3ameeting_ZWixNWRmNjctY2UzNC00MjYyLTk5NGEtMDIiYTFIZDNkMjBi%40thread.v2/0?context=%7b%22Tid%22%3a%22183ad437-6002-48ad-8886-c5885ce9be1a%22%2c%22Oid%22%3a%22a1686f0b-f6a4-4d27-9e45-ef2d33b9c41d%22%7d

Engagement strategy for patients: NA

Selection patients cases discussed in MTB

Selection criteria, number of cases discussed per MTB

From 1 to 40 cases are discussed per MTB

Any patient with a recurrent or metastatic cancer, or with a rare cancer who meets at least one of the three conditions below may be registered in the MTB by a referring physician:

- Patient had a consultation with one of the clinician of Institut Curie, and a pathology report is available in the medical record.
- Patient case previously discussed in a regional MTB for which Institut Curie is the reference center and a PFMG 2025 (SeqOIA) prescription has been validated.
- Patient referred to Institut Curie for a PFMG 2025 analysis under the pre-indications of "Rare Cancers" or "Metastatic adult solid tumour" (<https://pfmg2025.aviesan.fr/professionnels/pre-indications-et-mise-en-place/>), and frozen tumour material is available

Samples and data flow

General workflows of both samples and data for the NGS analysis

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

Figure 1: Institut Curie MTB workflow

The different steps of Institut Curie local MTB are :

- 1) the referring physician registers the patient for local MTB
- 2) **MTB 1 :**
 - Validation of the indication
 - Choice of samples/tools for the analyses : 2 possible workflows for molecular analyses via Institut Curie MTB:
 - a. **Internal prescription:** in-house DNA NGS panel (571 genes) for detection of : SNV, CNV, MSI status, TMB, HRD + targeted RNAseq panel for fusion detection.
 - b. **PFMG 2025 (SeqOIA) prescription:** WGS, WES and RNAseq for 2 pre-indications : "Rare Cancers" or "Metastatic adult solid tumour"
- 3) Pathological qualification of the sample + nucleic acids extraction
- 4) Clinical and biological data integration + molecular analyses
- 5) **MTB 2 :**
 - Review of the alterations validated by medical biologists
 - Proposition of a therapeutic solution and/or inclusion to a clinical trial based on a molecular alteration

Referring physicians are notified and invited to participate in the MTB 2 to discuss the reporting of results.

The MTB 2 conclusions are integrated directly into the Institut Curie medical file or send by email to the corresponding external referring physician.

Reporting of alterations

Somatic and germline alterations reporting in MTB conclusions

Somatic alterations are listed in a NGS report which is done by the molecular biologists and discussed in MTB. Somatic alterations reported by the molecular biologists are selected according to different levels of classification :

1. Gene classification as Oncogene or Tumor Suppressor Gene according to OncoKB database, COSMIC database and the literature
2. Variant classification:
 - a. Based on an in-house referential listing all previously validated variants in Institut Curie
 - b. Based on ACMG international classification that includes verification of international databases for variants classification :
 - ESP6500 & gnomAD for incidence in the general population
 - COSMIC, oncoKB & ClinVar for variant pathogenicity of all genes
 - IARC TP53 & BRCAshare for variant pathogenicity of specific genes

The classification allows to classify variants according to 5 different classes: pathogenic; likely pathogenic; variant of uncertain significance; likely benign; benign. The result is then adapted to somatic alterations taking into account the tumoral context (*e.g.* tumor cellularity, VAF, presence of signatures, LOH, variant expression when RNAseq is available, etc.)

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A MSI status, a score HRD, a TMB and the description of the mutational signature are also reported.

Discussions of the molecular reports in MTB allow to validate molecular alterations of interest for patient treatment, based on available clinical trials or targeted drugs, OncoKB classification and patient medical history (such as previous treatments received).

Both molecular reports and MTB conclusions are uploaded in the electronic medical record of the patient, and accessible to the referral oncologist.

Regarding germline alterations, MTB only reports suspicion of germline alteration based on the results of the somatic analysis. If a germline alteration is suspected, the MTB recommend to the physician to organize a genetic consultation for the patient, outside of the MTB.

During this genetic consultation, the oncogeneticist will then either prescribe an additional analysis to confirm the germline alteration, or give to the patient the results of the constitutional DNA (WES/WGS SeqOIA) analysis.

MTB endpoints and follow-up

Synthetic description of the endpoints :

A bi-annual assessment of MTB activity includes:

- Presentation of the number of cases discussed, molecular analyses, treatment propositions and inclusions into clinical trials
- Synthesis of the difficulties encountered and proposal of improvements,

If applicable, scientific publications

Endpoint categories (please check the following endpoints when relevant to your MTB) :

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Endpoint category	Endpoint subcategory	MTB endpoints <i>(check when relevant)</i>	Details
Patient/Healthcare professionals	Access to high throughput molecular screening	X	Number and type of molecular analyses per year and per tumor type
	Outcome	X	OS and PFS within specific projects
	Access to innovative drugs/trials	X	Treatment propositions and inclusions into clinical trials
	Patient-reported experience measures		NA
Healthcare providers and administrative	MTB activity	X	-Number of patients discussed in the MTB - Centralized screening for specific clinical trials - Scientific publications if applicable
	Process (workflows and communication)	X	Synthesis of the difficulties encountered and proposal of improvements
Economic impact	Medico-economic evaluation		NA

If applicable, which decision support tool (DST) does the MTB use?

(eg: OncoKDM, Navify, QCI Interpret, SeqOne, etc)

None

MTB ORGANIZATION

Institution	Institut Curie
Country	France
Type of MTB	National MTB for cancers of unknown primary

General description of MTB

Objectives, frequency, participants and roles, link to national initiatives...

Objectives:

The objective of the national RCP CUP is to organize the management of patients with metastatic cancer whose primary origin could not be determined on the histological markers independently of the stage of the disease and treatments received.

The national CUP MTB is part of the national initiative Plan France Médecine Génomique (PFMG) 2025 (<https://pfm2025.aviesan.fr/>) to validate indications for additional examinations and in particular the possibility of pan-genomic examinations. It also constitutes discussion on the NGS results.

Participants & Responsibilities :

Medical coordinators :

- Pr. Christophe Le Tourneau (Oncologist ; Institut Curie) et Dr Sarah Watson (Oncologist; Institut Curie).
- Pr. Janick Selves (Pathologist ; IUCT Oncopole de Toulouse).
- Dr. Etienne Rouleau (Biologist ; Gustave Roussy).

Referral oncologists for SeqOIA :

- Institut Curie : Pr. Christophe Le Tourneau et Dr Sarah Watson
- AP-HP : Dr. Camille Tlemsani
- Gustave Roussy : Dr. Anna Patrikidou

Experts committee at the national level :

- Vincent Cockenpot (Pathologist ; Centre Léon Bérard),
- Anne Salomon (Pathologist ; Institut Curie),
- Isabelle Soubeyran (Pathologist ; Institut Bergonié),
- Marius Ilié (Pathologist ; CHU Nice)
- Christelle de la Fouchardiere (Oncologist ; Centre Léon Bérard),
- Andy Karabajakian (Oncologist ; Centre Léon Bérard),
- Yann Loriot (Oncologist ; Gustave Roussy),
- Ivan Bièche (Biologist ; Institut Curie),
- Hélène Blons (Biologist ; APHP),
- Fabienne Escande (Biologist ; CHRU Lille),

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- Yves Allory (Pathologist ; Institut Curie)

Preparation and retranscription of this MTB is done by the same coordination team as the Institut Curie MTB under the scientific coordination of Maud Kamal, PhD (RCPmolCurieSequoia@curie.fr).

The MTB is headed by a medical coordinator and brings together several experts with complementary skills: oncologists, radiologists, pathologists, managers of molecular analysis platforms, bio-informaticians and biologists. The MTB relies on the presence of at least one oncologist, a pathologist, a biologist, and the scientific manager or molecular RCP project manager.

A coordination team is in charge of the MTB preparation and transcription

The medical coordinator must be an oncologist among 3 accredited experts who validates :

- The indication and prescription of molecular analyses for a given patient
- MTB reports and conclusions and orientation towards clinical trials

The MTB is a meeting opened to all national hospitals, facilities, and all experts referring a patient with CUP.

It is recommended that the prescribing physician be present at the national CUP MTB.

The prescribing physician is the doctor who will report the results to the patient. He/she agrees to :

- To complete the national CUP MTB form (patient registration information).
- Provide anatomopathological and molecular biology reports.
- Give the patient the information on the reuse of data and samples for research purposes and keep proof of this information in the medical file.

Frequency: Twice a month, on 2nd and 4th Thursdays at 5pm. Virtual meeting (Teams)

https://teams.microsoft.com/l/meetup-join/19%3ameeting_MGQ5ZTY5Y2YtODZiZi00MzRkLWI1NjMtODc4ZjAzNWVhNmE1%40thread.v2/0?content=%7b%22id%22%3a%22183ad437-6002-48ad-8886-c5885ce9be1a%22%2c%22oid%22%3a%22100dd442-689a-4e7b-b72c-c42786500b38%22%7d

Engagement strategy for patients: NA

Selection patients cases discussed in MTB

Selection criteria, number of cases discussed per MTB

From 1 to 20 cases are discussed per MTB

Any patient with metastatic cancer, for which the primary origin could not be determined. This preindication is limited to new incident cases.

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Samples and data flow

General workflows of both samples and data for the NGS analysis

Figure 1: National CUP MTB validation workflow (upper scheme) and analysis workflow (lower scheme)

The different steps of the National CUP MTB workflow are:

- 1) the referring physician registers the patient for national MTB
- 2) **MTB 1** :

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- Validation of the indication
- PFMG 2023 (SeqOIA [<https://laboratoire-segoia.fr/>] or AURAGEN [<https://www.auragen.fr/>] platform) prescription : WGS, WES and RNAseq
- 3) Medical consultation, signature of consent and samples shipment (tumor and blood) to corresponding sites for extraction and sequencing platform for sequencing
- 4) WES/WGS & RNAseq
- 5) Data integration
- 6) Validation of results and molecular reports
- 7) **MTB 2 :**
 - Review of the alterations reported by the molecular biologists
 - Proposition of a diagnosis and/or therapeutic solution (either based on the newly proposed diagnostic or based on a druggable molecular alteration)

Referring physicians are notified and invited to participate on both MTB 1 and MTB 2.

The MTB 2 conclusions and the molecular results are send by email to the corresponding external referring physician. For Institut Curie patients, both results and conclusions are also integrated directly into the medical record.

Reporting of alterations

Somatic and germline alterations reporting in MTB conclusions

Somatic alterations are listed in a NGS report which is done by the molecular biologists and discussed in MTB. Somatic alterations reported by the molecular biologists are selected according to different levels of classification :

1. Gene classification as Oncogene or Tumor Suppressor Gene according to OncoKB database, COSMIC database and the literature
2. Variant classification:
 - a. Based on an in-house referential listing all previously validated variants in Institut Curie
 - b. Based on ACMG international classification that includes verification of international databases for variants classification :
 - ESP6500 & gnomAD for incidence in the general population
 - COSMIC, oncoKB & ClinVar for variant pathogenicity of all genes
 - IARC TP53 & BRCAshare for variant pathogenicity of specific genes

The classification allows to classify variants according to 5 different classes: pathogenic; likely pathogenic; variant of uncertain significance; likely benign; benign. The result is then adapted to somatic alterations taking into account the tumoral context (e.g. tumor cellularity, VAF, presence of signatures, LOH, variant expression when RNAseq is available, etc.)

A MSI status, a score HRD, a TMB and the description of the mutational signature are also reported.

Since last year, a classifier tool based on the training of a variational autoencoder to predict tissue of origin based on the RNA-sequencing data developed by Dr Sarah Watson's team has been integrated into the analysis pipeline and is carried out on all SeqOIA CUP RNAseq data (Vibert et. al, 2021). This tool,

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combined with anatomopathological, molecular (DNA) and clinical data, can enable to refine diagnosis and consequent treatment.

Results of the classifier are validated by the molecular biologist according to the confidence scores (from 0 to 1) provided by 2 aligners software: Salmon and STAR.

Discussions in MTB 2 allows to :

- Validate molecular alterations of interest based on PFMG2025 analyses (WES/WGS/RNAseq)
- Discuss results of complementary analyses requested during MTB 1 (anatomopathological, clinical or molecular).
- Diagnostic precisions according to the different results, and suggestion of a presumed primary origin of the cancer.
- Treatment recommendations for patients and if possible orientation towards clinical trials
-

Both molecular reports and MTB conclusions are send to the referral physicians by email.

Regarding germline alterations, MTB only reports suspicion of germline alteration based on the results of the somatic analysis. If a germline alteration is suspected, the MTB recommend to the physician to organize a genetic consultation for the patient, outside of the MTB.

During this genetic consultation, the oncogeneticist will then either prescribe an additional analysis to confirm the germline alteration, or give to the patient the results of the constitutional DNA (WES/WGS SeqOIA) analysis.

MTB endpoints and follow-up

Synthetic description of the endpoints :

A bi-annual assessment of MTB activity includes:

- Presentation of the number of cases discussed, molecular analyses, treatment propositions and inclusions into clinical trials
- The following indicators:
 - Proportion of refined diagnoses thanks to : MTB recommendations, sequencing analyzes or other analyzes
 - Proportion of patients included in therapeutic trials.
- Synthesis of the difficulties encountered and proposal of improvements,
- If applicable, scientific publications

Endpoint categories (please check the following endpoints when relevant to your MTB) :

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Endpoint category	Endpoint subcategory	MTB endpoints <i>(check when relevant)</i>	Details
Patient/Healthcare professionals	Access to high throughput molecular screening	X	Number and type of molecular analyses per year and per tumor type
	Outcome	X	-OS and PFS within specific projects -Proposition of refined diagnosis
	Access to innovative drugs/trials	X	Treatment propositions and inclusions into clinical trials
	Patient-reported experience measures		NA
Healthcare providers and administrative	MTB activity	X	- Number of patients discussed in the MTB - Regions from where patients are addressed and treated - Centralized screening for specific clinical trials - Scientific publications if applicable
	Process (workflows and communication)	X	Synthesis of the difficulties encountered and proposal of improvements
Economic impact	Medico-economic evaluation		NA

If applicable, which decision support tool (DST) does the MTB use?

(eg: OncoKDM, Navify, QCI Interpret, SeqOne, etc)

None

MTB ORGANIZATION

Institution	Institut Català d'Oncologia (ICO)
Country	Spain
Participants to this form	Ernest Nadal, Daniel Azuara, Mireia Gausachs, Ània Alay, Carles Codony
Type of MTB	Local MTB

General description of MTB

Objectives, frequency, participants and multidisciplinary roles (medical, scientist, management and administrative if relevant), link to national initiatives, engagement strategy for patients ...

Objectives:

The organization: Catalan Institute of Oncology (ICO) is a public and monographic organization on cancer. ICO is distributed geographically in Catalonia in four university hospitals and 21 regional hospitals across the territory. Currently, ICO is the oncology center of reference for more than 40% of the adult population of Catalonia, corresponding to more than 35000 first visits per annum. The local molecular tumor board described corresponds to ICO-Hospitalet in the Hospital Duran i Reynals. ICO works in "functional units". The Oncological Functional Units are an organizational structure, which has professionals from the ICO and the Hospital Universitari of Bellvitge, based on the initial assessment of the patient by interdisciplinary teams specialized in each type of cancer. Unlike classic tumor committees, in functional units specialists share space during visits, bringing together medical oncologists, oncological surgeons, nursing professionals, radiation oncologists, radiologists, pathologists, and other specialists (such as gynecologists in the breast cancer unit, neurologists in neuro-oncology, pulmonologists, etc).

Objectives: As a part on the ICO's Precision Oncology Program the ICO-Hospitalet MTB refers patients with certain clinical contexts to molecular determination, allowing the selection of patients with molecular characteristic which in clinical studies have been associated with a better response to specific targeted treatments. The referred patients are selected based on level one genes and tumor types as described for the Catalan Health Service

(https://scientiasalut.gencat.cat/bitstream/handle/11351/9138/marcadors_farmacs_vinculats_programa_oncologia_precisio_2023.pdf?sequence=4&isAllowed=y) and subjected to reimbursement or with potential inclusion in active clinical trials.

Presently we are using two NGS solutions: TruSight Oncology 500 (Illumina) and OncoPrint Precision Assay (ThermoFisher). The results of each panel are discussed independently once a week.

Participants & Responsibilities (including administrative & medical management profiles if relevant):

Different participants are invited to the MTB:

- Clinical oncologists (ICO): Prescribing clinical oncologist are invited to present the clinical case for every sample. It is open to all medical oncologists interested in any case. Referral oncologist for different cancer types is present in the MTB.
- Bioinformatics (ICO-HUB): Analyses results are exposed by bioinformaticians and biologists.

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- Molecular Biologists (ICO-HUB): Analyses results are exposed by bioinformaticians and biologists.
- Pathologists (HUB): Referral pathologist for every cancer type explain the anatomic pathology of the different samples analyzed.
- Radiologists (HUB): Referral radiologists are invited.
- Genetic counseling specialists (ICO): Genetic counseling specialists evaluate potential hereditary cancer implications.
- Project manager (ICO-HUB): project managers contribute to clinical management of the MTB (disclosure of the cases that will be commented in each session to the corresponding specialists), management of the mailing and diffusion list, setting up the virtual MTB meetings, writing the minutes report for each MTB.

Each MTB requires at least the attendance of one clinical oncologist, one molecular biologist, one pathologist, one bioinformatician and one hereditary cancer specialist. The case is generally presented by the clinician and the results are then reported by the molecular biologist. All members participate in the discussion of the results and the results that will appear on the report are ratified.

In case no targeted therapy is available for reimbursement in the healthcare system (Sistema Català de Salut, CatSalut), clinicians from the Phase I clinical trials unit assess if there are open clinical trials for those patients that may not have other available treatment options.

Contact & links:

There is not any specific link or e-mail for our TMB.

Frequency: Targeted sequencing results are commented twice a week (Tuesday afternoon and Thursday morning).

Engagement strategy for patients: Not applicable. The prescribing clinical oncologist is in charge of communicating the results to the patient with the support of a clinical report generated after the MTB by the molecular biologists.

Sample selection criteria for MTB: Stage I to stage III lung cancer, metastatic colon cancer and cholangiocarcinoma patients are mainly sequenced using OncoPrint Precision Assay (OPA) technology, while other tumors, including but not limited to stage IV lung cancer, glioblastoma, endometrial cancer, breast cancer, melanoma, ovarian cancer (FIGO III, IV), or medullary thyroid cancer are sequenced using TruSight Oncology 500+ gene panel (TSO500).

Samples and data flow

General workflows of both samples and data for the NGS analysis

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TruSight Oncology 500 kit(Illumina)

This targeted sequencing panel covers the detection of small variants (SNV and indels) in 523 genes, copy number alterations in 59 genes, fusions in 55 genes and splice variants in 3 genes. Additionally, TMB and MSI are also assessed.

Input requirement for library preparation: 40ng of DNA and 40-80ng of RNA are needed.

Run sequencing: Libraries (paired DNA+RNA) from 8 samples are sequenced in a NextSeq 550 Dx.

Turn-around time (TAT): approximately 10 days.

OncoPrint Precision Assay Gx (ThermoFisher)

This targeted sequencing panel covers the detection of small variants (SNV and indels) in 45 genes, copy number alterations in 14 genes, fusions in 16 genes, and splice variants in 3 genes.

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10ng of DNA and 10ng of RNA are needed, and the runs (sequenced in the integrated Ion Torrent Genexus platform) allocate from 4 to 16 samples (paired DNA+RNA) by batched of 4 samples (4,8,12,16).

Turn-around time (TAT) is of approximately 5 days.

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The different steps for the HUB-ICO MTB are:

- 1) The referring physician registers the sample in the SAP application (APA or LCAM depending on the tumor)
- 2) The application is accepted and processed to Anatomical Pathology department
- 3) Archival samples are identified and processed
- 4) DNA and RNA extraction
- 5) Library preparation + Sequencing
- 6) Data analysis
- 7) Curations of variants (manual)
- 8) Discussion of the results to identify potential treatments and clinical trials.

Reporting of alterations

Somatic and germline alterations reporting in MTB conclusions

Somatic alterations are described in the NGS report, which is done by molecular biologists and discussed in MTB. Classification based on CatSalut's guidelines, in Tiers (oncoKB) and ESCAT classification.

The report includes: Patient ID , diagnosis and pathology; justification of the molecular study, results (divided between targetable alterations and not targetable alterations), interpretation of the molecular results, methodology, limitations and other considerations.

Identification of putative germline alterations is done systematically, and when a germline alteration is suspected, the variant is studied by the germline committee. If a pathogenic variant is suspected to be germline (following the ESMO guidelines), the patient will be referred to the genetic counseling Unit.

MTB endpoints and follow-up

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Synthetic description of the endpoints :

Endpoint categories (please check the following endpoints when relevant to your MTB) :

Endpoint category	Endpoint subcategory	MTB endpoints (check when relevant)	Details
Patient/Healthcare professionals	Access to high throughput molecular screening	x	
	Outcome	x	
	Access to innovative drugs/trials	x	
	Patient-reported experience measures		NA
Healthcare providers and administrative	MTB activity	x	
	Process (workflows and communication)	x	
Economic impact	Medico-economic evaluation	x	

If applicable, which decision support tool (DST) does the MTB use?

(eg: OncoKDM, Navify, QCI Interpret, SeqOne, etc)

The use of public databases such as ClinVar or gnomAD is used in the bioinformatics pipeline to annotate the results and manual variant curation is supported by literature search, Navify mutation profiler, Alamut, and Franklin genome databases

MTB ORGANIZATION

Institution	University Clinical Center, Medical University of Warsaw
Country	Poland
Participants to this form	Tomasz Stokłosa
Type of MTB	Local MTB for patients with tumors of the CNS

General description of MTB

Objectives, frequency, participants and multidisciplinary roles (medical, scientist, management and administrative if relevant), link to national initiatives, engagement strategy for patients ...

Objectives: University Clinical Center of Medical University of Warsaw (UCK WUM) aims to consult and discuss patients who are treated in the Dept of Neurosurgery with gliomas and other tumors of the CNS (including metastatic cancer to the brain) towards an integrated pathological and molecular diagnosis and also to guide patient to a clinical trial with innovative molecules if applicable, based on the tumor molecular characterisation.

Participants & Responsibilities (including administrative & medical management profiles if relevant) :

Medical Coordinator and Organizers: Prof. Przemysław Kunert, MD, PhD, Chief of Dept of Neurosurgery University Clinical Center MUW, neurosurgeon, Tomasz Stokłosa, Geneticist, Head of Laboratory of Genetics

Participants:

- Prof. Przemysław Kunert, MD, PhD and Dept of Neurosurgery clinical staff (Tomasz Dzedzic, MD, PhD, Kacper Koczyk, MD) and psychologist
- Clinical oncologist (Prf. Rafał Stec, MD, PhD)
- Radiooncologists (Prof. Joanna Kunikowska, MD, PhD,)
- Radiotherapist (Prof. Lucyna Kępa, MD, PhD)
- Pathologist (Łukasz Michałowski, MD, PhD)
- Geneticist, Head of Laboratory of Genetics (Prof. Tomasz Stokłosa, Md, PhD)

The MTB is headed by Chief of Dept of Neurosurgery, Professor Przemysław Kunert and brings together several experts with complementary skills: oncologists, radiologists, pathologists, lab geneticist responsible for molecular analysis platforms,

The MTB is a meeting opened to :

- All members of the UCK WUM, however upon invitation.

Contact & links:

Personal e-mails

Frequency: Ad hoc

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Engagement strategy for patients: N/A

Selection patients cases discussed in MTB

Selection criteria, number of cases discussed per MTB

From 1 to 5 cases are discussed per MTB

Any patient with a brain tumor (either CNS origin or metastatic) who needs to be discussed

- Either before neurosurgery (to discuss treatment and diagnostic options)
- Or after neurosurgery when the pathology report and/or genetical report is available in the medical record.

Samples and data flow

General workflows of both samples and data for the NGS analysis

Targeted DNA seq with custom-designed panel encompassing more than 300 genes, followed by SNV and CNV analysis. Additionally methylation of MGMT promotor is assessed by commercially available qPCR test

Reporting of alterations

Somatic and germline alterations reporting in MTB conclusions

Somatic and germline alterations are listed in a NGS report which is done by the molecular biologists and discussed in MTB. (if the germline variant is suspected, additional consulting and verification is scheduled) Somatic alterations reported by the molecular biologists and lab geneticist are selected according to different levels of classification :

1. Variant classification:
 - a. Based on an in-house referential listing all previously validated variants in MUW
 - b. Based on AMP/ACMG international classification that includes verification of international databases for variants classification :
 - ESP6500 & gnomAD for incidence in the general population
 - COSMIC, & ClinVar for variant pathogenicity of all genes
- The classification allows to classify variants according to 4 different classes as recommended for somatic variants: pathogenic; likely pathogenic; variant of uncertain significance; benign. The result is then adapted to somatic alterations taking into account the tumoral context (*e.g.* tumor cellularity, VAF, CNV, LOH, etc.)

MTB endpoints and follow-up

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Synthetic description of the endpoints :

Too early stage of MTB introduction at UCK WUM to precise

Endpoint categories (please check the following endpoints when relevant to your MTB) :

Endpoint category	Endpoint subcategory	MTB endpoints <i>(check when relevant)</i>	Details
Patient/Healthcare professionals	Access to high throughput molecular screening		
	Outcome		
	Access to innovative drugs/trials		
	Patient-reported experience measures		
Healthcare providers and administrative	MTB activity		
	Process (workflows and communication)		
Economic impact	Medico-economic evaluation		

If applicable, which decision support tool (DST) does the MTB use?

(eg: OncoKDM, Navify, QCI Interpret, SeqOne, etc)

None yet

MTB ORGANIZATION

Institution	Maria Sklodowska Curie National Research Institute of Oncology
Country	Poland
Participants to this form	Iwona Lugowska
Type of MTB	Preliminary steps (not implemented yet)

General description of MTB

Objectives, frequency, participants and multidisciplinary roles (medical, scientist, management and administrative if relevant), link to national initiatives, engagement strategy for patients ...

Objectives:

In rare cancer populations or in patients who failed to the standard of care to verify additional therapeutic options.

But, it is possible to do molecular testing within clinical trials (preferable) or commercially (large panels are not reimbursed, and patients must pay from their pocket) or in some institutions, there is possible to perform a 30 genes NGS panel (like in the MSCI). However, only in selected indications, it is reimbursed.

Participants & Responsibilities (including administrative & medical management profiles if relevant):

In the MSCI, the Centre for Excellence for Precision Oncology was established to organize precision oncology in our hospital. We are responsible for consulting patients, performing research and to organize MTB.

We usually consult around 1000 patients per year as a collaboration with the Early Phase Clinical Trials Dept. We are a Partner of the Research Consortia (CanHeal, PrimeRose and PCM4EU), but we were not able to organize the MTB with the involvement of a multidisciplinary team. The main limitation is lack of time and, second - lack of personnel.

With 2000 cancer patients per day, the need of multidisciplinary team meetings for EVERY patient newly diagnosed (must be done to get reimbursement), our attempts to get additional time with the clinician responsible for the patient, overloaded pathologists, and molecular biologists failed.

We are open to discussion how to make it more feasible within our limitations. Perhaps a discussion about some IT solutions or other channels of communication or patient selection to the MTB may work.

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So far. We only verify the FMI reports, and clinical oncologist involved in clinical studies decides about the option for patients, and the patient is informed about the decision. Only in case of questions about specific mutations in the report, we are in contact with molecular biologists.

Contact & links:

Iwona Lugowska, Iwona.Lugowska@nio.gov.pl

Frequency:

Once a week, we have around 15 reports, so we analyse those report when they are realized

Engagement strategy for patients:

Not in place, we need to discuss

Samples and data flow

General workflows of both samples and data for the NGS analysis

We are using Foundation One reports or similar which are available only as a part of clinical trials. The reimbursement for molecular testing is only available if there is access to targeted therapies defined by the National Health Found eg BRAF mutation in melanoma for adjuvant and metastatic patients because we have access to inhibitors for this indication.

Reporting of alterations

Somatic and germline alterations reporting in MTB conclusions

As above

MTB endpoints and follow-up

Endpoint category	Endpoint subcategory	MTB endpoints <i>(check when relevant)</i>	Details
Patient/Healthcare professionals	Access to high throughput molecular screening		Limited, as above
	Outcome		We have data based with 5000 consulted patients and 50% of them have a MFI report. Not yet analysed
	Access to innovative drugs/trials		As a part of collaboration with Early Phase Dept. (80 early phase clinical trials over the last 5 years)
	Patient-reported experience measures		None
Healthcare providers and administrative	MTB activity		Need for find the optimal and feasible solution

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	Process (workflows and communication)		
Economic impact	Medico-economic evaluation		Very difficult to assess, no data so far, there must be a balance between staff engagement and HTA

Synthetic description of the endpoints :

Endpoint categories (please check the following endpoints when relevant to your MTB) :

If applicable, which decision support tool (DST) does the MTB use?

(eg: OncoKDM, Navify, QCI Interpret, SeqOne, etc)

Not yet selected, but in future, we would like to implement the most user friendly software

MTB ORGANIZATION

Institution	CHU LILLE
Country	FRANCE
Participants to this form	
Type of MTB	LOCAL MTB

General description of MTB

Objectives, frequency, participants and multidisciplinary roles (medical, scientist, management and administrative if relevant), link to national initiatives, engagement strategy for patients ...

Objectives: The objective of the local MTB is to organize the management of patients with solid tumors requiring molecular diagnostics.

The meeting offers to identify molecular alterations (mutations, fusions, amplifications) and/or anatomo-pathological alterations (over-expression, histological transformations) using the techniques available at Lille University Hospital, the Oscar Lambret Center and in partnership with the SEQOIA laboratory, in order to guide patients towards a treatment adapted to the molecular alterations identified.

Participants & Responsibilities (including administrative & medical management profiles if relevant):

Coordinator:

- Pr Cortot Alexis (MD, Pneumologist, Oncologist; Chu Lille)
- Dr Farchi Olivier (Molecular biologist; Chu Lille)
- Dr Descarpentries Clothilde (Molecular Biologist; Chu Lille)
- Dr Escande Fabienne (Molecular biologist; Chu Lille)

MTB Members :

- Dr Lebellec Loic (MD, Oncologist; Oscar Lambret Center Lille)
- Mrs Gregoire Valérie (Biologist, Chu Lille)
- Dr Turpin Anthony (MD, Oncologist, CHU Lille)

Administrative profiles

- Mrs Urbain Pauline (MTB secretary; Chu Lille)

Other profiles

- Mrs Candaele Stéphanie (Seqoia prescription assistant, Chu Lille)

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Preparation and reporting (letters) of this MTB is done by the secretary at CHU Lille on behalf of medical coordinator Teams.

The meeting is open to all physicians wishing to refer a patient with a solid tumor requiring molecular diagnostics in the Nord and Pas-de-Calais departments. Registration is performed by filling a form via the webDCR software.

The MTB is headed by a medical coordinator and brings together several experts with complementary skills: Oncologists, pathologists, biologists, organ physicians.

The MTB relies on the presence of at least one molecular biologist, an oncologist, and the medical coordinator or a session moderator (Oncologist or Molecular biologist)

The MTB validates :

- the indication and prescription of molecular analyses
- interpretation of the test results
- help with complex results
- reports and conclusions,
- orientation towards clinical trials and/or adapted treatments

It is recommended that the referent physician of the patient participates to the MTB. He agrees:

- to complete the MTB Form in webDCR Software patient.
- to provide pathological and molecular biology reports
- to give the patient the information about the use of data and biological samples for.

Contact & links:

<https://dcc.onco-hdf.fr>

Pauline.urbain@chu-lille.fr

Frequency: Twice a month on 1st and 3rd Tuesday at 12h30 pm. virtual meeting (Teams)

Engagement strategy for patients: on physician's request if he wants to add some molecular tests, or to have explanations about previously realized tests. On biologist's request if he wants to present particular and useful results of molecular tests for a patient.

Selection patients cases discussed in MTB:

Selection criteria ,number of cases discussed per MTB

The number of files per MTB is not limited.

Any patient with solid Tumor , whatever the stage of the disease , with 2 months predicted Overall survival

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

Samples and data flow

General workflows of both samples and data for the NGS analysis

The different steps of the local MTB workflow are:

- 1) the referring physician registers the patient for Local MTB
- 2) **MTB 1**

validation of the indication

check tissue availability and quality

NGS DNA panels (small panel for routine analysis and large panel for MTB-patients), targeted RNASeq, MSI analysis, methylation analysis (MGMT, MLH1, methylome, CGH-array)

Do files have to be discussed a second time when results are returned?

not systematically, only in case of result allowing potentially the use of targeted therapy, or in case of result with complex interpretation

Reporting of alterations

Somatic and germline alterations reporting in MTB conclusions

We report only somatic alterations. The molecular report also mentions the type of tests that has been used, the genes that have been tested, and whether there are known to be associated with sensitivity or resistance to therapies. The report of the MTB mentions the clinical trials that may be suitable for the patient, and/or the treatment that is recommended by the MTB.

MTB endpoints and follow-up

Synthetic description of the endpoints:

- Indicator : number of discussed patients : For 2022 : 250 discussed patients, for 2021 : 130 discussed patients, For 2020 : 100 patients

Endpoint category	Endpoint subcategory	MTB endpoints (<i>check when relevant</i>)	Details
Patient/Healthcare professionals	Access to high throughput molecular screening	×	Number and type of molecular analyses per year and per tumor type
	Outcome	×	-Os and PFS within specific projects -Proposition of refined diagnosis
	Access to innovative drugs/trials	×	Treatment propositions and inclusions into clinical trials
	Patient-reported experience measures		NA
Healthcare providers and administrative	MTB activity	×	-number of patients discussed in the MTB -regions from where patients are addressed and treated -screening for clinical trials
	Process (workflows and communication)	×	
Economic impact	Medico-economic evaluation		

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision *via* MTB

If applicable, which decision support tool (DST) does the MTB use?

(eg: OncoKDM, Navify, QCI Interpret, SeqOne, etc)

- We don't use a tool in particular, but any useful tool in adequacy with each situation. Collegial discussions using the specialists' expertise guarantees optimal patient care.